

Supplementary material for the article:
A survey-review of online methods for change point detection
in ion-mobility spectrometry data

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2 Algorithms excluding bad channels

As mentioned in the article, there are channels that do not contain variability or show only binary noise. Initially, the ground truths were defined for such channels and the algorithms measured MAE-scores regardless of the quality of a channel. However, this approach can decrease accuracy of the MAE-scores.

For addressing this problems we modified the algorithms. The improved algorithms calculate differences between the minimum and the maximum value in an initial sample. If the difference is less than a certain value, then the channel is excluded from calculations and do not contribute to MAE-scores.

2.1 Mushrooms mix

2.1.1 Baseline1

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 1: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 2: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 3: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	14	5	13	18	20	30	12
		10	15	22	24	30	19
		15	13	24	30	30	24
IMS_abs2	14	5	13	17	20	43	12
		10	17	23	24	43	19
		15	13	27	30	43	24
IMS_abs3	14	5	13	13	20	17	12
		10	13	15	24	17	19
		15	13	17	30	17	24
IMS_abs4	18	5	13	6	20	14	12
		10	13	12	24	14	19
		15	16	33	30	14	24
IMS_abs5	18	5	16	22	20	14	12
		10	15	26	24	14	19
		15	16	29	30	14	24
IMS_abs6	18	5	18	20	20	22	12
		10	15	24	24	22	19
		15	16	28	30	22	24
IMS_abs7	18	5	20	20	20	22	12
		10	15	23	24	22	19
		15	15	26	30	22	24
IMS_abs9	18	5	13	8	20	16	12
		10	13	13	24	16	19
		15	13	16	30	16	24
IMS_abs10	18	5	13	8	20	16	12
		10	16	16	24	16	19
		15	13	17	30	16	24
IMS_abs11	18	5	20	21	20	14	12
		10	15	25	24	14	19
		15	15	28	30	14	24
IMS_abs12	18	5	13	6	20	14	12
		10	23	11	24	14	19
		15	17	32	30	14	24
IMS_abs13	18	5	13	6	20	14	12
		10	13	12	24	14	19
		15	17	40	30	14	24
IMS_abs14	19	5	13	7	20	14	12
		10	13	12	24	14	19
		15	17	16	30	14	24
IMS_abs15	19	5	13	7	20	63	12
		10	13	13	24	63	19
		15	17	16	30	63	24
mean run time (msec)			3.083	2.927	1.222	65.584	0.487
mean relative run time			6.334	6.015	2.511	134.755	1.000

Table 2: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 1.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	3.29	7.07	2.71	9.21	5.29
10	3.64	5.93	6.71	9.21	1.71
15	2.21	8.93	12.71	9.21	6.71

Table 3: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 1.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 4: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 5: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 6: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 15.

2.1.2 Baseline2

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 7: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 8: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 9: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	15	5	17	12	16	21	14
		10	13	16	19	21	19
		15	13	19	23	21	22
IMS_abs2	15	5	17	14	16	21	14
		10	13	16	19	21	19
		15	13	19	23	21	22
IMS_abs3	17	5	16	12	16	103	14
		10	14	17	19	103	19
		15	14	20	23	103	22
IMS_abs4	17	5	16	13	16	20	14
		10	13	16	19	20	19
		15	13	20	23	20	22
IMS_abs5	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	21	excluded
		10	13	16	19	21	19
		15	13	19	23	21	22
IMS_abs6	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	13	19	23	excluded	22
IMS_abs7	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	26	5	13	14	16	103	14
		10	13	16	19	103	19
		15	13	18	23	103	22
IMS_abs10	18	5	13	7	16	103	14
		10	13	20	19	103	19
		15	14	20	23	103	22
IMS_abs11	35	5	14	7	16	103	14
		10	13	12	19	103	19
		15	14	18	23	103	22
IMS_abs12	35	5	14	10	16	44	14
		10	13	11	19	44	19
		15	16	16	23	44	22
IMS_abs13	35	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs14	19	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	19	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			3.059	6.942	0.847	133.463	0.492
mean relative run time			6.216	14.106	1.720	271.214	1.000

Table 6: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 2.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	8.25	11.12	6.75	38.22	8.25
10	8.56	7.00	6.00	38.22	6.00
15	7.60	6.40	7.20	38.22	6.80

Table 7: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 2.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 10: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 11: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 12: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	14	5	17	12	16	21	14
		10	13	16	19	21	19
		15	13	19	23	21	22
IMS_abs2	14	5	17	14	16	21	14
		10	13	16	19	21	19
		15	13	19	23	21	22
IMS_abs3	14	5	16	12	16	103	14
		10	14	17	19	103	19
		15	14	20	23	103	22
IMS_abs4	15	5	16	13	16	20	14
		10	13	16	19	20	19
		15	13	20	23	20	22
IMS_abs5	15	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	21	excluded
		10	13	16	19	21	19
		15	13	19	23	21	22
IMS_abs6	15	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	13	19	23	excluded	22
IMS_abs7	18	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	23	5	13	14	16	103	14
		10	13	16	19	103	19
		15	13	18	23	103	22
IMS_abs10	18	5	13	7	16	103	14
		10	13	20	19	103	19
		15	14	20	23	103	22
IMS_abs11	35	5	14	7	16	103	14
		10	13	12	19	103	19
		15	14	18	23	103	22
IMS_abs12	35	5	14	10	16	44	14
		10	13	11	19	44	19
		15	16	16	23	44	22
IMS_abs13	35	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs14	19	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	19	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			3.126	6.971	0.841	134.175	0.497
mean relative run time			6.288	14.021	1.692	269.870	1.000

Table 8: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix table 2.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	8.25	9.88	6.75	39.56	7.00
10	7.22	7.22	6.67	39.56	6.67
15	6.20	7.20	8.00	39.56	7.60

Table 9: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix table 2.

2.1.3 Baseline3

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 13: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 14: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 15: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	16	5	15	19	19	22	12
		10	14	21	23	22	22
		15	14	22	25	22	23
IMS_abs2	16	5	13	9	19	36	12
		10	13	20	23	36	22
		15	13	20	25	36	23
IMS_abs3	13	5	13	8	19	18	12
		10	14	17	23	18	22
		15	13	17	25	18	23
IMS_abs4	17	5	16	6	19	16	12
		10	16	26	23	16	22
		15	16	31	25	16	23
IMS_abs5	17	5	18	20	19	14	12
		10	16	24	23	14	22
		15	15	25	25	14	23
IMS_abs6	17	5	17	20	19	22	12
		10	17	22	23	22	22
		15	15	22	25	22	23
IMS_abs7	17	5	16	20	19	21	12
		10	19	21	23	21	22
		15	15	21	25	21	23
IMS_abs9	19	5	13	6	19	19	12
		10	13	11	23	19	22
		15	13	16	25	19	23
IMS_abs10	16	5	13	8	19	18	12
		10	13	14	23	18	22
		15	13	17	25	18	23
IMS_abs11	19	5	16	21	19	16	12
		10	16	25	23	16	22
		15	16	27	25	16	23
IMS_abs12	19	5	16	6	19	13	12
		10	16	26	23	13	22
		15	16	30	25	13	23
IMS_abs13	19	5	16	6	19	13	12
		10	16	26	23	13	22
		15	16	30	25	13	23
IMS_abs14	19	5	16	6	19	15	12
		10	16	25	23	15	22
		15	16	30	25	15	23
IMS_abs15	19	5	16	excluded	19	58	12
		10	16	25	23	58	22
		15	16	22	25	58	23
mean run time (msec)			3.110	4.074	1.074	65.665	0.498
mean relative run time			6.243	8.178	2.157	131.822	1.000

Table 10: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 3.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	2.21	8.29	1.64	7.43	5.36
10	2.43	5.71	5.64	7.43	4.64
15	2.57	6.64	7.64	7.43	5.64

Table 11: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 3.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 16: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 17: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 18: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	17	5	14	10	14	82	13
		10	14	15	13	82	18
		15	14	20	21	82	22
IMS_abs2	17	5	14	10	14	22	13
		10	14	15	13	22	18
		15	15	19	21	22	22
IMS_abs3	24	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	103	excluded
		10	14	17	13	103	18
		15	14	19	21	103	22
IMS_abs4	24	5	15	10	14	21	13
		10	14	14	13	21	18
		15	14	18	21	21	22
IMS_abs5	24	5	14	10	14	34	13
		10	14	14	13	34	18
		15	13	18	21	34	22
IMS_abs6	24	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	103	excluded
		10	13	14	13	103	18
		15	13	18	21	103	22
IMS_abs7	24	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	18	5	16	12	14	103	13
		10	13	17	13	103	18
		15	13	20	21	103	22
IMS_abs10	18	5	14	10	14	103	13
		10	13	16	13	103	18
		15	16	20	21	103	22
IMS_abs11	24	5	14	6	14	103	13
		10	14	16	13	103	18
		15	14	18	21	103	22
IMS_abs12	22	5	14	12	14	103	13
		10	14	14	13	103	18
		15	14	21	21	103	22
IMS_abs13	22	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	103	excluded
		10	16	16	13	103	18
		15	16	21	21	103	22
IMS_abs14	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			4.259	7.773	8.078	231.907	0.509
mean relative run time			8.364	15.264	15.863	455.379	1.000

Table 12: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix table 3.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	6.12	10.50	6.50	59.27	7.50
10	7.36	6.00	8.27	59.27	3.64
15	7.09	3.64	2.82	59.27	2.55

Table 13: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix table 3.

2.1.4 Baseline4

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 19: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 20: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 21: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	18	5	19	21	16	33	12
		10	18	22	22	33	22
		15	17	24	21	33	24
IMS_abs2	18	5	14	21	16	25	12
		10	17	22	22	25	22
		15	15	24	21	25	24
IMS_abs3	15	5	14	16	16	44	12
		10	14	18	22	44	22
		15	13	19	21	44	24
IMS_abs4	19	5	13	6	16	13	12
		10	13	11	22	13	22
		15	17	16	21	13	24
IMS_abs5	19	5	23	6	16	24	12
		10	18	26	22	24	22
		15	17	31	21	24	24
IMS_abs6	19	5	22	22	16	22	12
		10	18	24	22	22	22
		15	17	25	21	22	24
IMS_abs7	19	5	21	21	16	15	12
		10	16	22	22	15	22
		15	18	23	21	15	24
IMS_abs9	19	5	13	7	16	72	12
		10	13	12	22	72	22
		15	13	17	21	72	24
IMS_abs10	16	5	13	9	16	21	12
		10	14	14	22	21	22
		15	14	19	21	21	24
IMS_abs11	19	5	16	22	16	22	12
		10	16	25	22	22	22
		15	16	27	21	22	24
IMS_abs12	19	5	16	6	16	17	12
		10	16	27	22	17	22
		15	16	32	21	17	24
IMS_abs13	19	5	13	6	16	17	12
		10	16	11	22	17	22
		15	17	16	21	17	24
IMS_abs14	19	5	16	6	16	14	12
		10	13	11	22	14	22
		15	16	16	21	14	24
IMS_abs15	19	5	16	6	16	57	12
		10	16	excluded	22	57	22
		15	16	16	21	57	24
mean run time (msec)			3.620	3.958	0.912	86.922	0.530
mean relative run time			6.836	7.475	1.722	164.149	1.000

Table 14: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 4.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	3.43	8.00	2.50	12.64	6.36
10	2.79	6.57	3.64	12.64	3.64
15	2.50	5.43	2.64	12.64	5.64

Table 15: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 4.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 22: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 23: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 24: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 15.

2.1.5 Baseline5

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 25: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 26: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 27: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	18	5	15	20	19	42	12
		10	18	21	17	42	21
		15	15	23	25	42	24
IMS_abs2	18	5	17	17	19	46	12
		10	16	21	17	46	21
		15	13	25	25	46	24
IMS_abs3	17	5	13	14	19	16	12
		10	15	15	17	16	21
		15	13	17	25	16	24
IMS_abs4	17	5	15	9	19	14	12
		10	14	25	17	14	21
		15	15	28	25	14	24
IMS_abs5	17	5	15	11	19	12	12
		10	14	23	17	12	21
		15	15	23	25	12	24
IMS_abs6	17	5	15	11	19	13	12
		10	14	20	17	13	21
		15	15	21	25	13	24
IMS_abs7	17	5	15	10	19	20	12
		10	16	19	17	20	21
		15	15	20	25	20	24
IMS_abs9	18	5	13	6	19	17	12
		10	13	11	17	17	21
		15	16	46	25	17	24
IMS_abs10	18	5	13	7	19	17	12
		10	13	15	17	17	21
		15	13	16	25	17	24
IMS_abs11	18	5	15	20	19	21	12
		10	15	23	17	21	21
		15	15	24	25	21	24
IMS_abs12	18	5	15	21	19	12	12
		10	15	26	17	12	21
		15	15	29	25	12	24
IMS_abs13	18	5	15	11	19	12	12
		10	16	26	17	12	21
		15	16	30	25	12	24
IMS_abs14	17	5	15	10	19	18	12
		10	16	26	17	18	21
		15	15	29	25	18	24
IMS_abs15	17	5	15	10	19	65	12
		10	16	25	17	65	21
		15	15	28	25	65	24
mean run time (msec)			2.934	3.121	0.952	68.546	0.514
mean relative run time			5.705	6.070	1.852	133.309	1.000

Table 18: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 5.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	2.79	5.86	1.50	9.57	5.50
10	2.43	5.36	0.50	9.57	3.50
15	2.79	8.43	7.50	9.57	6.50

Table 19: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 28: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 29: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 30: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	20	5	14	6	14	32	13
		10	13	11	17	32	17
		15	13	16	26	32	24
IMS_abs2	20	5	14	7	14	36	13
		10	13	12	17	36	17
		15	19	16	26	36	24
IMS_abs3	20	5	13	8	14	92	13
		10	13	12	17	92	17
		15	16	23	26	92	24
IMS_abs4	20	5	13	11	14	28	13
		10	13	12	17	28	17
		15	19	25	26	28	24
IMS_abs5	20	5	13	6	14	35	13
		10	13	13	17	35	17
		15	19	25	26	35	24
IMS_abs6	20	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs7	20	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	26	5	15	12	14	103	13
		10	15	16	17	103	17
		15	13	20	26	103	24
IMS_abs10	18	5	13	8	14	103	13
		10	14	21	17	103	17
		15	13	20	26	103	24
IMS_abs11	25	5	15	11	14	103	13
		10	13	16	17	103	17
		15	13	34	26	103	24
IMS_abs12	25	5	14	11	14	99	13
		10	14	15	17	99	17
		15	14	20	26	99	24
IMS_abs13	25	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	14	21	26	excluded	24
IMS_abs14	19	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	19	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			3.260	5.382	0.843	154.607	0.483
mean relative run time			6.744	11.135	1.744	319.864	1.000

Table 20: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix table 5.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	7.78	12.67	7.56	48.56	8.56
10	8.11	8.00	4.56	48.56	4.56
15	6.60	4.70	4.10	48.56	3.10

Table 21: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix table 5.

2.2 Black chanterelle

2.2.1 Baseline1

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 31: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 32: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 33: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	18	5	13	8	20	93	10
		10	13	26	17	93	18
		15	13	29	25	93	24
IMS_abs2	18	5	13	6	20	82	10
		10	13	12	17	82	18
		15	13	17	25	82	24
IMS_abs3	18	5	13	6	20	15	10
		10	13	12	17	15	18
		15	16	30	25	15	24
IMS_abs4	18	5	13	6	20	14	10
		10	13	13	17	14	18
		15	18	30	25	14	24
IMS_abs5	18	5	13	6	20	14	10
		10	18	29	17	14	18
		15	18	29	25	14	24
IMS_abs6	18	5	17	6	20	14	10
		10	18	26	17	14	18
		15	18	29	25	14	24
IMS_abs7	18	5	17	22	20	33	10
		10	18	24	17	33	18
		15	17	28	25	33	24
IMS_abs9	18	5	13	6	20	16	10
		10	13	12	17	16	18
		15	18	16	25	16	24
IMS_abs10	18	5	13	7	20	17	10
		10	13	15	17	17	18
		15	13	17	25	17	24
IMS_abs11	18	5	17	22	20	14	10
		10	15	25	17	14	18
		15	17	28	25	14	24
IMS_abs12	18	5	13	6	20	12	10
		10	13	11	17	12	18
		15	17	32	25	12	24
IMS_abs13	18	5	13	6	20	12	10
		10	13	12	17	12	18
		15	17	33	25	12	24
IMS_abs14	18	5	13	6	20	16	10
		10	13	12	17	16	18
		15	17	33	25	16	24
IMS_abs15	18	5	13	7	20	57	10
		10	13	12	17	57	18
		15	17	33	25	57	24
mean run time (msec)			2.942	2.800	0.983	89.762	0.463
mean relative run time			6.355	6.049	2.124	193.901	1.000

Table 22: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle flask 1.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	4.14	10.57	2.00	16.36	8.00
10	3.79	6.50	1.00	16.36	0.00
15	1.64	10.00	7.00	16.36	6.00

Table 23: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle flask 1.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 34: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 35: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 36: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 15.

2.2.2 Baseline2

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 37: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 38: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 39: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 15.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 40: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 41: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 42: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	10	5	13	8	11	18	12
		10	13	13	17	18	17
		15	13	17	21	18	21
IMS_abs2	10	5	13	7	11	103	12
		10	13	11	17	103	17
		15	13	16	21	103	21
IMS_abs3	25	5	13	12	11	103	12
		10	13	14	17	103	17
		15	13	17	21	103	21
IMS_abs4	25	5	13	8	11	17	12
		10	13	13	17	17	17
		15	13	17	21	17	21
IMS_abs5	25	5	13	9	11	26	12
		10	13	13	17	26	17
		15	13	17	21	26	21
IMS_abs6	25	5	14	9	11	103	12
		10	13	14	17	103	17
		15	13	17	21	103	21
IMS_abs7	25	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	15	5	15	13	11	103	12
		10	15	16	17	103	17
		15	13	20	21	103	21
IMS_abs10	15	5	14	11	11	94	12
		10	16	16	17	94	17
		15	15	20	21	94	21
IMS_abs11	55	5	15	12	11	103	12
		10	14	16	17	103	17
		15	13	20	21	103	21
IMS_abs12	55	5	15	11	11	102	12
		10	14	20	17	102	17
		15	15	20	21	102	21
IMS_abs13	55	5	16	11	11	103	12
		10	13	20	17	103	17
		15	16	21	21	103	21
IMS_abs14	55	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	55	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			3.437	6.885	0.702	207.237	0.441
mean relative run time			7.786	15.597	1.590	469.424	1.000

Table 28: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle table 2.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	15.73	18.55	18.00	52.36	17.36
10	16.27	14.64	14.91	52.36	14.91
15	16.09	14.45	13.82	52.36	13.82

Table 29: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle table 2.

2.2.3 Baseline3

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 43: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 44: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 45: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	18	5	16	6	22	55	10
		10	15	27	25	55	16
		15	17	32	24	55	20
IMS_abs2	18	5	15	6	22	103	10
		10	17	22	25	103	16
		15	17	23	24	103	20
IMS_abs3	18	5	13	7	22	18	10
		10	13	16	25	18	16
		15	13	17	24	18	20
IMS_abs4	18	5	13	6	22	17	10
		10	13	11	25	17	16
		15	13	16	24	17	20
IMS_abs5	18	5	13	6	22	17	10
		10	18	11	25	17	16
		15	16	16	24	17	20
IMS_abs6	18	5	21	6	22	17	10
		10	18	27	25	17	16
		15	16	32	24	17	20
IMS_abs7	18	5	22	excluded	22	17	10
		10	18	27	25	17	16
		15	16	31	24	17	20
IMS_abs9	18	5	13	7	22	19	10
		10	13	12	25	19	16
		15	13	17	24	19	20
IMS_abs10	18	5	13	7	22	17	10
		10	13	12	25	17	16
		15	14	19	24	17	20
IMS_abs11	18	5	16	6	22	17	10
		10	18	28	25	17	16
		15	16	34	24	17	20
IMS_abs12	18	5	13	6	22	17	10
		10	13	11	25	17	16
		15	16	16	24	17	20
IMS_abs13	18	5	13	6	22	17	10
		10	13	12	25	17	16
		15	13	16	24	17	20
IMS_abs14	18	5	13	6	22	17	10
		10	13	12	25	17	16
		15	13	16	24	17	20
IMS_abs15	18	5	13	6	22	68	10
		10	13	12	25	68	16
		15	13	16	24	68	20
mean run time (msec)			2.986	3.667	1.163	91.585	0.402
mean relative run time			7.435	9.131	2.897	228.065	1.000

Table 30: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle flask 3.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	4.21	12.21	4.00	13.00	8.00
10	3.14	6.71	7.00	13.00	2.00
15	3.29	5.50	6.00	13.00	2.00

Table 31: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle flask 3.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 46: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 47: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 48: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	27	5	14	10	13	19	14
		10	14	14	17	19	18
		15	13	18	20	19	21
IMS_abs2	27	5	15	11	13	19	14
		10	13	15	17	19	18
		15	13	18	20	19	21
IMS_abs3	27	5	14	11	13	21	14
		10	13	14	17	21	18
		15	13	16	20	21	21
IMS_abs4	27	5	13	12	13	16	14
		10	13	14	17	16	18
		15	13	18	20	16	21
IMS_abs5	27	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	18	excluded
		10	13	14	17	18	18
		15	13	18	20	18	21
IMS_abs6	27	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	13	18	20	excluded	21
IMS_abs7	27	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	15	5	14	12	13	103	14
		10	14	16	17	103	18
		15	13	21	20	103	21
IMS_abs10	15	5	14	11	13	48	14
		10	14	16	17	48	18
		15	13	18	20	48	21
IMS_abs11	15	5	16	6	13	103	14
		10	14	excluded	17	103	18
		15	16	16	20	103	21
IMS_abs12	25	5	17	6	13	103	14
		10	17	20	17	103	18
		15	17	22	20	103	21
IMS_abs13	20	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs14	27	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	27	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			2.613	3.440	0.693	113.222	0.470
mean relative run time			5.554	7.313	1.474	240.692	1.000

Table 32: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle table 3.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	7.88	12.38	9.25	36.56	8.25
10	8.89	9.56	7.11	36.56	6.78
15	9.70	6.90	6.20	36.56	5.80

Table 33: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle table 3.

2.2.4 Baseline4

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 49: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 50: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 51: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	14	5	13	17	20	56	12
		10	14	19	24	56	18
		15	13	24	25	56	24
IMS_abs2	17	5	13	7	20	13	12
		10	13	12	24	13	18
		15	13	16	25	13	24
IMS_abs3	17	5	15	6	20	13	12
		10	13	12	24	13	18
		15	15	27	25	13	24
IMS_abs4	17	5	15	10	20	13	12
		10	14	25	24	13	18
		15	15	27	25	13	24
IMS_abs5	17	5	15	10	20	13	12
		10	14	24	24	13	18
		15	15	27	25	13	24
IMS_abs6	17	5	15	10	20	13	12
		10	16	23	24	13	18
		15	15	27	25	13	24
IMS_abs7	17	5	15	10	20	30	12
		10	16	23	24	30	18
		15	15	22	25	30	24
IMS_abs9	19	5	13	6	20	16	12
		10	13	13	24	16	18
		15	17	16	25	16	24
IMS_abs10	19	5	13	15	20	17	12
		10	13	16	24	17	18
		15	13	17	25	17	24
IMS_abs11	17	5	16	22	20	13	12
		10	14	24	24	13	18
		15	16	27	25	13	24
IMS_abs12	17	5	16	6	20	13	12
		10	22	11	24	13	18
		15	16	29	25	13	24
IMS_abs13	17	5	13	6	20	13	12
		10	13	12	24	13	18
		15	16	30	25	13	24
IMS_abs14	17	5	13	6	20	15	12
		10	13	12	24	15	18
		15	16	30	25	15	24
IMS_abs15	17	5	13	6	20	51	12
		10	13	12	24	51	18
		15	16	16	25	51	24
mean run time (msec)			2.793	2.646	1.124	60.609	0.474
mean relative run time			5.890	5.580	2.371	127.831	1.000

Table 34: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle flask 4.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	2.93	8.43	2.93	9.14	5.07
10	3.43	5.64	6.93	9.14	1.21
15	2.00	7.86	7.93	9.14	6.93

Table 35: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle flask 4.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 52: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 53: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 54: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	21	5	13	6	10	28	10
		10	21	26	13	28	24
		15	17	27	23	28	27
IMS_abs2	18	5	15	6	10	29	10
		10	18	24	13	29	24
		15	17	26	23	29	27
IMS_abs3	23	5	13	6	10	103	10
		10	21	28	13	103	24
		15	16	30	23	103	27
IMS_abs4	18	5	16	6	10	28	10
		10	16	24	13	28	24
		15	16	26	23	28	27
IMS_abs5	18	5	18	21	10	36	10
		10	16	22	13	36	24
		15	16	25	23	36	27
IMS_abs6	18	5	15	6	10	103	10
		10	16	23	13	103	24
		15	16	25	23	103	27
IMS_abs7	18	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	18	5	16	15	10	103	10
		10	15	20	13	103	24
		15	15	22	23	103	27
IMS_abs10	18	5	15	15	10	103	10
		10	14	20	13	103	24
		15	16	22	23	103	27
IMS_abs11	18	5	14	7	10	103	10
		10	14	21	13	103	24
		15	14	26	23	103	27
IMS_abs12	25	5	15	10	10	103	10
		10	15	17	13	103	24
		15	14	20	23	103	27
IMS_abs13	25	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs14	18	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	18	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			3.738	7.228	0.629	176.629	0.561
mean relative run time			6.662	12.883	1.121	314.803	1.000

Table 36: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle table 4.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	4.50	10.30	9.50	54.40	9.50
10	2.90	4.60	6.50	54.40	4.70
15	3.80	6.40	3.90	54.40	7.50

Table 37: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle table 4.

2.2.5 Baseline5

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 55: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 56: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 57: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	15	5	13	9	11	45	12
		10	13	16	25	45	18
		15	13	18	25	45	23
IMS_abs2	21	5	13	8	11	14	12
		10	13	12	25	14	18
		15	20	16	25	14	23
IMS_abs3	18	5	13	6	11	14	12
		10	13	11	25	14	18
		15	16	28	25	14	23
IMS_abs4	18	5	18	6	11	14	12
		10	15	26	25	14	18
		15	16	28	25	14	23
IMS_abs5	18	5	17	21	11	13	12
		10	15	25	25	13	18
		15	16	28	25	13	23
IMS_abs6	18	5	17	12	11	14	12
		10	21	24	25	14	18
		15	16	28	25	14	23
IMS_abs7	18	5	16	10	11	30	12
		10	16	23	25	30	18
		15	16	22	25	30	23
IMS_abs9	18	5	13	6	11	17	12
		10	13	11	25	17	18
		15	16	32	25	17	23
IMS_abs10	18	5	13	7	11	17	12
		10	13	16	25	17	18
		15	13	17	25	17	23
IMS_abs11	18	5	15	20	11	14	12
		10	14	23	25	14	18
		15	15	27	25	14	23
IMS_abs12	18	5	15	21	11	12	12
		10	15	26	25	12	18
		15	16	29	25	12	23
IMS_abs13	18	5	15	6	11	12	12
		10	13	11	25	12	18
		15	16	30	25	12	23
IMS_abs14	18	5	13	6	11	16	12
		10	13	12	25	16	18
		15	16	30	25	16	23
IMS_abs15	18	5	13	6	11	59	12
		10	13	12	25	59	18
		15	16	16	25	59	23
mean run time (msec)			3.050	2.732	0.949	61.079	0.464
mean relative run time			6.570	5.885	2.044	131.555	1.000

Table 38: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle flask 5.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	3.43	8.86	7.00	9.07	6.00
10	4.14	6.00	7.00	9.07	0.43
15	2.21	8.07	7.00	9.07	5.00

Table 39: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle flask 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 58: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 59: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 60: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	32	5	13	12	9	22	12
		10	15	15	29	22	17
		15	13	18	27	22	22
IMS_abs2	32	5	13	10	9	22	12
		10	13	13	29	22	17
		15	23	16	27	22	22
IMS_abs3	32	5	13	8	9	100	12
		10	14	13	29	100	17
		15	13	18	27	100	22
IMS_abs4	32	5	13	9	9	27	12
		10	13	13	29	27	17
		15	13	17	27	27	22
IMS_abs5	32	5	13	9	9	96	12
		10	13	13	29	96	17
		15	13	17	27	96	22
IMS_abs6	32	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	103	excluded
		10	14	13	29	103	17
		15	13	16	27	103	22
IMS_abs7	32	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	26	5	13	10	9	103	12
		10	14	17	29	103	17
		15	13	20	27	103	22
IMS_abs10	26	5	13	7	9	103	12
		10	14	15	29	103	17
		15	13	16	27	103	22
IMS_abs11	26	5	13	6	9	103	12
		10	15	11	29	103	17
		15	15	32	27	103	22
IMS_abs12	17	5	15	19	9	103	12
		10	15	21	29	103	17
		15	15	21	27	103	22
IMS_abs13	26	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs14	26	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	26	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			3.856	7.791	1.011	187.720	0.465
mean relative run time			8.289	16.750	2.174	403.566	1.000

Table 40: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle table 5.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	15.11	18.78	19.33	54.50	16.33
10	14.70	15.10	3.90	54.50	11.70
15	14.30	11.60	4.30	54.50	7.70

Table 41: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle table 5.

2.3 Yellowfoot

2.3.1 Baseline1

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 61: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 62: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 63: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	16	5	13	19	15	19	17
		10	13	20	28	19	18
		15	13	21	27	19	22
IMS_abs2	16	5	13	17	15	19	17
		10	13	19	28	19	18
		15	13	20	27	19	22
IMS_abs3	16	5	13	14	15	15	17
		10	13	14	28	15	18
		15	13	17	27	15	22
IMS_abs4	16	5	13	13	15	15	17
		10	13	14	28	15	18
		15	18	34	27	15	22
IMS_abs5	16	5	21	24	15	15	17
		10	16	43	28	15	18
		15	17	30	27	15	22
IMS_abs6	16	5	16	22	15	15	17
		10	16	26	28	15	18
		15	17	30	27	15	22
IMS_abs7	16	5	18	21	15	16	17
		10	16	25	28	16	18
		15	16	29	27	16	22
IMS_abs9	14	5	13	14	15	17	17
		10	13	16	28	17	18
		15	13	18	27	17	22
IMS_abs10	14	5	13	16	15	17	17
		10	13	17	28	17	18
		15	13	18	27	17	22
IMS_abs11	18	5	17	21	15	15	17
		10	16	24	28	15	18
		15	15	29	27	15	22
IMS_abs12	18	5	13	7	15	15	17
		10	13	13	28	15	18
		15	17	34	27	15	22
IMS_abs13	18	5	13	7	15	15	17
		10	13	14	28	15	18
		15	17	16	27	15	22
IMS_abs14	18	5	13	7	15	15	17
		10	13	14	28	15	18
		15	13	16	27	15	22
IMS_abs15	18	5	13	7	15	15	17
		10	13	14	28	15	18
		15	13	16	27	15	22
mean run time (msec)			2.746	3.147	1.368	43.873	0.494
mean relative run time			5.553	6.364	2.767	88.725	1.000

Table 42: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 1.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	3.00	5.50	1.71	2.21	1.29
10	2.57	6.07	11.57	2.21	1.57
15	2.14	7.86	10.57	2.21	5.57

Table 43: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 1.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 64: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 65: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 66: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	22	5	14	16	10	28	12
		10	14	24	16	28	18
		15	13	25	23	28	23
IMS_abs2	22	5	14	7	10	32	12
		10	17	28	16	32	18
		15	19	28	23	32	23
IMS_abs3	18	5	14	8	10	103	12
		10	13	14	16	103	18
		15	13	19	23	103	23
IMS_abs4	20	5	14	11	10	26	12
		10	14	16	16	26	18
		15	13	22	23	26	23
IMS_abs5	20	5	14	10	10	28	12
		10	14	16	16	28	18
		15	13	24	23	28	23
IMS_abs6	20	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs7	20	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	18	5	13	9	10	33	12
		10	13	12	16	33	18
		15	13	19	23	33	23
IMS_abs10	25	5	13	9	10	103	12
		10	13	13	16	103	18
		15	14	excluded	23	103	23
IMS_abs11	30	5	14	8	10	30	12
		10	14	18	16	30	18
		15	14	20	23	30	23
IMS_abs12	30	5	14	10	10	23	12
		10	14	14	16	23	18
		15	14	19	23	23	23
IMS_abs13	17	5	14	9	10	101	12
		10	14	14	16	101	18
		15	14	19	23	101	23
IMS_abs14	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			3.098	6.528	0.694	122.277	0.477
mean relative run time			6.497	13.690	1.456	256.434	1.000

Table 44: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 1.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	8.40	12.50	12.20	29.90	10.20
10	8.20	6.90	6.20	29.90	4.40
15	8.20	6.50	4.00	29.90	4.00

Table 45: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 1.

2.3.2 Baseline2

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 67: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 68: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 69: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	15	5	13	14	21	20	14
		10	13	19	24	20	20
		15	13	20	26	20	22
IMS_abs2	15	5	13	9	21	19	14
		10	13	17	24	19	20
		15	13	18	26	19	22
IMS_abs3	14	5	14	15	21	16	14
		10	14	16	24	16	20
		15	13	18	26	16	22
IMS_abs4	18	5	13	6	21	16	14
		10	13	12	24	16	20
		15	15	16	26	16	22
IMS_abs5	17	5	17	21	21	16	14
		10	17	26	24	16	20
		15	15	30	26	16	22
IMS_abs6	17	5	17	21	21	16	14
		10	17	25	24	16	20
		15	15	28	26	16	22
IMS_abs7	17	5	18	20	21	22	14
		10	17	25	24	22	20
		15	15	26	26	22	22
IMS_abs9	15	5	13	6	21	18	14
		10	13	12	24	18	20
		15	13	16	26	18	22
IMS_abs10	15	5	13	6	21	18	14
		10	13	17	24	18	20
		15	13	17	26	18	22
IMS_abs11	17	5	15	6	21	16	14
		10	15	11	24	16	20
		15	15	31	26	16	22
IMS_abs12	18	5	13	6	21	16	14
		10	13	11	24	16	20
		15	16	32	26	16	22
IMS_abs13	18	5	15	6	21	16	14
		10	13	11	24	16	20
		15	15	32	26	16	22
IMS_abs14	18	5	15	6	21	16	14
		10	13	11	24	16	20
		15	15	32	26	16	22
IMS_abs15	18	5	15	6	21	18	14
		10	17	11	24	18	20
		15	15	31	26	18	22
mean run time (msec)			2.705	2.666	1.148	50.210	0.617
mean relative run time			4.386	4.323	1.862	81.427	1.000

Table 46: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 2.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	2.14	7.71	4.43	2.36	2.57
10	2.21	5.57	7.43	2.36	3.43
15	2.21	8.50	9.43	2.36	5.43

Table 47: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 2.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 70: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 71: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 72: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	18	5	13	7	9	103	11
		10	19	30	22	103	19
		15	18	34	24	103	23
IMS_abs2	18	5	13	7	9	103	11
		10	13	12	22	103	19
		15	18	34	24	103	23
IMS_abs3	18	5	16	19	9	103	11
		10	16	20	22	103	19
		15	16	21	24	103	23
IMS_abs4	19	5	13	6	9	64	11
		10	18	11	22	64	19
		15	17	34	24	64	23
IMS_abs5	19	5	13	6	9	66	11
		10	13	11	22	66	19
		15	18	16	24	66	23
IMS_abs6	19	5	13	6	9	103	11
		10	13	11	22	103	19
		15	18	16	24	103	23
IMS_abs7	19	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	17	5	16	15	9	20	11
		10	14	19	22	20	19
		15	14	20	24	20	23
IMS_abs10	17	5	13	15	9	20	11
		10	13	17	22	20	19
		15	13	19	24	20	23
IMS_abs11	18	5	15	11	9	21	11
		10	14	16	22	21	19
		15	14	20	24	21	23
IMS_abs12	18	5	14	16	9	20	11
		10	14	19	22	20	19
		15	14	20	24	20	23
IMS_abs13	18	5	14	18	9	52	11
		10	14	19	22	52	19
		15	14	20	24	52	23
IMS_abs14	18	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	18	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			2.981	3.874	0.809	159.111	0.471
mean relative run time			6.336	8.233	1.719	338.132	1.000

Table 48: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 2.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	4.18	6.82	9.09	43.27	7.09
10	3.64	4.55	3.91	43.27	0.91
15	2.27	6.09	5.91	43.27	4.91

Table 49: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 2.

2.3.3 Baseline3

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 73: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 74: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 75: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	16	5	13	19	20	25	19
		10	16	22	16	25	20
		15	13	24	18	25	24
IMS_abs2	16	5	13	18	20	21	19
		10	13	20	16	21	20
		15	13	22	18	21	24
IMS_abs3	13	5	13	14	20	15	19
		10	14	14	16	15	20
		15	13	17	18	15	24
IMS_abs4	17	5	15	6	20	15	19
		10	13	11	16	15	20
		15	15	30	18	15	24
IMS_abs5	17	5	14	9	20	13	19
		10	14	25	16	13	20
		15	15	29	18	13	24
IMS_abs6	17	5	14	11	20	15	19
		10	14	24	16	15	20
		15	14	27	18	15	24
IMS_abs7	17	5	14	19	20	21	19
		10	14	23	16	21	20
		15	14	22	18	21	24
IMS_abs9	14	5	13	6	20	18	19
		10	13	16	16	18	20
		15	13	16	18	18	24
IMS_abs10	14	5	13	7	20	18	19
		10	13	17	16	18	20
		15	13	17	18	18	24
IMS_abs11	16	5	14	8	20	15	19
		10	14	26	16	15	20
		15	14	29	18	15	24
IMS_abs12	17	5	14	7	20	15	19
		10	14	11	16	15	20
		15	14	30	18	15	24
IMS_abs13	17	5	14	7	20	15	19
		10	16	11	16	15	20
		15	14	30	18	15	24
IMS_abs14	17	5	14	7	20	15	19
		10	16	12	16	15	20
		15	14	29	18	15	24
IMS_abs15	17	5	14	7	20	35	19
		10	16	12	16	35	20
		15	14	19	18	35	24
mean run time (msec)			2.386	2.677	0.804	52.124	0.565
mean relative run time			4.220	4.735	1.422	92.195	1.000

Table 50: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 3.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	2.36	6.86	3.93	4.36	2.93
10	1.93	5.36	1.07	4.36	3.93
15	2.29	8.29	1.93	4.36	7.93

Table 51: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 3.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 76: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 77: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 78: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	15	5	17	13	14	72	14
		10	14	17	15	72	18
		15	14	20	24	72	22
IMS_abs2	15	5	14	12	14	24	14
		10	14	15	15	24	18
		15	14	19	24	24	22
IMS_abs3	35	5	14	8	14	103	14
		10	15	18	15	103	18
		15	13	18	24	103	22
IMS_abs4	35	5	16	12	14	26	14
		10	13	15	15	26	18
		15	14	19	24	26	22
IMS_abs5	35	5	16	11	14	26	14
		10	13	13	15	26	18
		15	13	18	24	26	22
IMS_abs6	35	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	103	excluded
		10	13	12	15	103	18
		15	13	18	24	103	22
IMS_abs7	35	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	10	5	14	10	14	26	14
		10	15	15	15	26	18
		15	14	19	24	26	22
IMS_abs10	10	5	13	10	14	26	14
		10	13	14	15	26	18
		15	13	19	24	26	22
IMS_abs11	22	5	15	9	14	24	14
		10	14	21	15	24	18
		15	13	20	24	24	22
IMS_abs12	22	5	14	12	14	21	14
		10	14	17	15	21	18
		15	14	19	24	21	22
IMS_abs13	22	5	14	12	14	73	14
		10	14	17	15	73	18
		15	13	19	24	73	22
IMS_abs14	22	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	18	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			3.243	6.141	0.771	123.867	0.483
mean relative run time			6.711	12.710	1.595	256.351	1.000

Table 52: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 3.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	9.20	11.20	9.70	27.82	9.70
10	10.91	9.45	10.09	27.82	9.27
15	11.09	9.27	8.73	27.82	8.18

Table 53: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 3.

2.3.4 Baseline4

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 79: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 80: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 81: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	10	5	13	13	10	20	14
		10	13	15	20	20	20
		15	13	18	24	20	24
IMS_abs2	10	5	13	10	10	14	14
		10	13	13	20	14	20
		15	13	17	24	14	24
IMS_abs3	15	5	14	8	10	10	14
		10	19	23	20	10	20
		15	20	26	24	10	24
IMS_abs4	16	5	13	6	10	10	14
		10	19	20	20	10	20
		15	13	23	24	10	24
IMS_abs5	16	5	13	18	10	10	14
		10	13	19	20	10	20
		15	13	23	24	10	24
IMS_abs6	16	5	13	17	10	19	14
		10	13	18	20	19	20
		15	13	20	24	19	24
IMS_abs7	16	5	13	16	10	18	14
		10	13	17	20	18	20
		15	13	18	24	18	24
IMS_abs9	16	5	14	6	10	12	14
		10	20	26	20	12	20
		15	15	28	24	12	24
IMS_abs10	16	5	13	10	10	12	14
		10	22	11	20	12	20
		15	16	29	24	12	24
IMS_abs11	16	5	13	7	10	29	14
		10	14	20	20	29	20
		15	14	24	24	29	24
IMS_abs12	17	5	14	7	10	12	14
		10	20	24	20	12	20
		15	14	27	24	12	24
IMS_abs13	17	5	14	7	10	12	14
		10	20	24	20	12	20
		15	14	26	24	12	24
IMS_abs14	17	5	14	7	10	13	14
		10	20	23	20	13	20
		15	14	26	24	13	24
IMS_abs15	17	5	13	7	10	27	14
		10	14	22	20	27	20
		15	14	25	24	27	24
mean run time (msec)			2.961	2.678	0.815	43.775	0.510
mean relative run time			5.808	5.253	1.600	85.863	1.000

Table 54: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 4.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	2.86	6.29	5.36	5.79	2.50
10	3.29	5.00	4.64	5.79	4.64
15	2.71	8.21	8.64	5.79	8.64

Table 55: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 4.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 82: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 83: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 84: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	18	5	17	22	16	45	14
		10	16	24	18	45	19
		15	16	24	22	45	24
IMS_abs2	17	5	16	12	16	47	14
		10	14	19	18	47	19
		15	15	22	22	47	24
IMS_abs3	18	5	14	6	16	88	14
		10	13	30	18	88	19
		15	13	31	22	88	24
IMS_abs4	18	5	15	23	16	44	14
		10	16	24	18	44	19
		15	16	24	22	44	24
IMS_abs5	17	5	15	12	16	68	14
		10	15	16	18	68	19
		15	16	23	22	68	24
IMS_abs6	17	5	16	12	16	103	14
		10	14	16	18	103	19
		15	16	22	22	103	24
IMS_abs7	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	18	5	14	14	16	103	14
		10	15	16	18	103	19
		15	13	21	22	103	24
IMS_abs10	18	5	14	8	16	103	14
		10	15	21	18	103	19
		15	15	20	22	103	24
IMS_abs11	25	5	13	13	16	27	14
		10	13	14	18	27	19
		15	13	17	22	27	24
IMS_abs12	24	5	16	12	16	103	14
		10	13	16	18	103	19
		15	13	19	22	103	24
IMS_abs13	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	103	excluded
		10	13	16	18	103	19
		15	13	20	22	103	24
IMS_abs14	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			3.480	6.322	0.825	196.059	0.517
mean relative run time			6.734	12.234	1.597	379.421	1.000

Table 56: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 4.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	4.00	7.40	3.00	57.00	5.00
10	4.55	4.82	1.55	57.00	2.18
15	4.36	5.64	4.09	57.00	5.36

Table 57: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 4.

2.3.5 Baseline5

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 85: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 86: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 87: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	16	5	13	19	12	21	12
		10	16	22	16	21	19
		15	14	22	28	21	23
IMS_abs2	15	5	13	9	12	22	12
		10	13	21	16	22	19
		15	13	20	28	22	23
IMS_abs3	13	5	13	14	12	15	12
		10	15	14	16	15	19
		15	13	17	28	15	23
IMS_abs4	18	5	13	6	12	15	12
		10	13	11	16	15	19
		15	15	30	28	15	23
IMS_abs5	17	5	20	21	12	15	12
		10	16	25	16	15	19
		15	15	29	28	15	23
IMS_abs6	17	5	18	20	12	15	12
		10	16	24	16	15	19
		15	15	26	28	15	23
IMS_abs7	17	5	16	19	12	21	12
		10	14	23	16	21	19
		15	15	22	28	21	23
IMS_abs9	18	5	13	6	12	17	12
		10	13	11	16	17	19
		15	16	16	28	17	23
IMS_abs10	18	5	13	6	12	17	12
		10	13	13	16	17	19
		15	13	16	28	17	23
IMS_abs11	17	5	15	13	12	15	12
		10	14	24	16	15	19
		15	15	29	28	15	23
IMS_abs12	17	5	15	6	12	15	12
		10	14	11	16	15	19
		15	15	31	28	15	23
IMS_abs13	17	5	14	6	12	15	12
		10	14	11	16	15	19
		15	15	31	28	15	23
IMS_abs14	17	5	14	9	12	15	12
		10	14	13	16	15	19
		15	15	29	28	15	23
IMS_abs15	17	5	14	8	12	46	12
		10	14	13	16	46	19
		15	14	29	28	46	23
mean run time (msec)			2.729	2.711	0.853	53.969	0.473
mean relative run time			5.769	5.730	1.804	114.074	1.000

Table 58: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 5.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	2.71	7.00	4.71	4.57	4.71
10	2.79	5.71	1.29	4.57	2.29
15	2.21	8.64	11.29	4.57	6.29

Table 59: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 88: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 89: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 90: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
IMS_abs1	19	5	14	11	14	23	15
		10	13	15	20	23	20
		15	14	20	21	23	22
IMS_abs2	19	5	14	12	14	25	15
		10	14	18	20	25	20
		15	14	20	21	25	22
IMS_abs3	21	5	13	10	14	103	15
		10	14	15	20	103	20
		15	13	19	21	103	22
IMS_abs4	24	5	13	14	14	22	15
		10	13	17	20	22	20
		15	13	19	21	22	22
IMS_abs5	24	5	15	12	14	103	15
		10	14	17	20	103	20
		15	13	19	21	103	22
IMS_abs6	24	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	14	19	21	excluded	22
IMS_abs7	24	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs9	18	5	14	6	14	103	15
		10	15	19	20	103	20
		15	13	24	21	103	22
IMS_abs10	25	5	14	excluded	14	103	15
		10	15	17	20	103	20
		15	13	16	21	103	22
IMS_abs11	17	5	13	8	14	103	15
		10	13	13	20	103	20
		15	13	18	21	103	22
IMS_abs12	17	5	13	10	14	103	15
		10	13	16	20	103	20
		15	13	20	21	103	22
IMS_abs13	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs14	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
IMS_abs15	17	5	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		10	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
		15	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded	excluded
mean run time (msec)			2.965	4.111	0.804	169.982	0.522
mean relative run time			5.680	7.875	1.539	325.601	1.000

Table 60: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 5.

moving window size	shewhart(e)	cusum(e)	max mcusum(e)	bayes(e)	mfcusum(e)
5	6.78	11.22	6.44	56.44	5.44
10	6.67	4.33	2.67	56.44	2.67
15	7.50	3.80	2.80	56.44	3.00

Table 61: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 5.

3 Algorithms not excluding bad channels

3.1 Mushrooms mix

3.1.1 Baseline1

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 91: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 92: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 93: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	14	5	6	18	18	30	6
		10	11	22	22	30	11
		15	16	24	28	30	16
IMS_abs2	14	5	5	17	18	43	6
		10	10	23	22	43	11
		15	15	27	28	43	16
IMS_abs3	14	5	6	13	18	17	6
		10	11	15	22	17	11
		15	15	17	28	17	16
IMS_abs4	18	5	5	6	18	14	6
		10	10	12	22	14	11
		15	15	33	28	14	16
IMS_abs5	18	5	9	22	18	14	6
		10	20	26	22	14	11
		15	19	29	28	14	16
IMS_abs6	18	5	9	20	18	22	6
		10	14	24	22	22	11
		15	19	28	28	22	16
IMS_abs7	18	5	9	20	18	22	6
		10	10	23	22	22	11
		15	18	26	28	22	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	6	8	18	16	6
		10	10	13	22	16	11
		15	15	16	28	16	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	8	18	16	6
		10	11	16	22	16	11
		15	16	17	28	16	16
IMS_abs11	18	5	5	21	18	14	6
		10	10	25	22	14	11
		15	18	28	28	14	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	5	6	18	14	6
		10	10	11	22	14	11
		15	15	32	28	14	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	6	6	18	14	6
		10	11	12	22	14	11
		15	15	40	28	14	16
IMS_abs14	19	5	6	7	18	14	6
		10	11	12	22	14	11
		15	15	16	28	14	16
IMS_abs15	19	5	6	7	18	63	6
		10	11	13	22	63	11
		15	16	16	28	63	16
mean run time (msec)			1.601	3.390	0.937	60.951	0.160
mean relative run time			10.007	21.188	5.858	380.994	1.000

Table 62: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 1.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	10.93	7.07	1.00	9.21	11.29
10	6.14	5.93	4.71	9.21	6.29
15	1.93	8.93	10.71	9.21	2.14

Table 63: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 1.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 94: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 95: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 96: Mushrooms mix Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	20	5	6	6	9	32	6
		10	15	29	31	32	13
		15	20	29	17	32	18
IMS_abs2	20	5	8	22	9	69	6
		10	15	27	31	69	13
		15	19	29	17	69	18
IMS_abs3	20	5	5	7	9	154	6
		10	10	24	31	154	13
		15	15	24	17	154	18
IMS_abs4	20	5	5	6	9	112	6
		10	15	26	31	112	13
		15	20	28	17	112	18
IMS_abs5	20	5	6	6	9	114	6
		10	10	24	31	114	13
		15	15	28	17	114	18
IMS_abs6	20	5	6	6	9	0	6
		10	15	23	31	0	13
		15	17	26	17	0	18
IMS_abs7	20	5	7	7	9	265	6
		10	10	23	31	265	13
		15	15	28	17	265	18
IMS_abs9	19	5	6	9	9	0	6
		10	11	14	31	0	13
		15	17	20	17	0	18
IMS_abs10	16	5	7	10	9	0	6
		10	12	13	31	0	13
		15	15	18	17	0	18
IMS_abs11	19	5	5	11	9	22	6
		10	11	16	31	22	13
		15	16	20	17	22	18
IMS_abs12	19	5	7	11	9	21	6
		10	12	17	31	21	13
		15	17	20	17	21	18
IMS_abs13	19	5	5	10	9	0	6
		10	10	15	31	0	13
		15	15	19	17	0	18
IMS_abs14	19	5	5	10	9	259	6
		10	10	19	31	259	13
		15	15	20	17	259	18
IMS_abs15	19	5	5	0	9	248	6
		10	10	0	31	248	13
		15	15	27	17	248	18
mean run time (msec)			1.342	7.231	0.655	531.301	0.167
mean relative run time			8.027	43.268	3.919	3178.940	1.000

Table 64: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix table 1.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	13.36	10.93	10.29	83.86	13.29
10	7.43	5.14	11.71	83.86	6.29
15	2.79	4.71	2.43	83.86	1.57

Table 65: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix table 1.

3.1.2 Baseline2

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 97: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 98: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 99: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	15	5	9	12	14	21	5
		10	11	16	17	21	10
		15	16	19	21	21	16
IMS_abs2	15	5	6	14	14	21	5
		10	10	16	17	21	10
		15	16	19	21	21	16
IMS_abs3	17	5	5	12	14	292	5
		10	10	17	17	292	10
		15	15	20	21	292	16
IMS_abs4	17	5	9	13	14	20	5
		10	11	16	17	20	10
		15	16	20	21	20	16
IMS_abs5	17	5	9	13	14	21	5
		10	11	16	17	21	10
		15	16	19	21	21	16
IMS_abs6	17	5	5	14	14	140	5
		10	11	16	17	140	10
		15	15	19	21	140	16
IMS_abs7	17	5	5	12	14	266	5
		10	10	16	17	266	10
		15	15	20	21	266	16
IMS_abs9	26	5	5	14	14	0	5
		10	10	16	17	0	10
		15	15	18	21	0	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	7	14	0	5
		10	10	20	17	0	10
		15	17	20	21	0	16
IMS_abs11	35	5	5	7	14	0	5
		10	10	12	17	0	10
		15	15	18	21	0	16
IMS_abs12	35	5	5	10	14	44	5
		10	10	11	17	44	10
		15	15	16	21	44	16
IMS_abs13	35	5	5	0	14	0	5
		10	10	0	17	0	10
		15	17	17	21	0	16
IMS_abs14	19	5	0	0	14	258	5
		10	12	12	17	258	10
		15	20	20	21	258	16
IMS_abs15	19	5	0	0	14	250	5
		10	0	0	17	250	10
		15	0	0	21	250	16
mean run time (msec)			9.012	14.418	0.582	533.863	0.113
mean relative run time			80.083	128.124	5.174	4744.029	1.000

Table 66: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 2.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	16.29	12.43	7.57	89.93	16.57
10	11.86	9.00	5.14	89.93	11.57
15	7.14	7.50	6.14	89.93	5.86

Table 67: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 2.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 100: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 101: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 102: Mushrooms mix Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	14	5	9	12	14	21	5
		10	11	16	17	21	10
		15	16	19	21	21	16
IMS_abs2	14	5	6	14	14	21	5
		10	10	16	17	21	10
		15	16	19	21	21	16
IMS_abs3	14	5	5	12	14	292	5
		10	10	17	17	292	10
		15	15	20	21	292	16
IMS_abs4	15	5	9	13	14	20	5
		10	11	16	17	20	10
		15	16	20	21	20	16
IMS_abs5	15	5	9	13	14	21	5
		10	11	16	17	21	10
		15	16	19	21	21	16
IMS_abs6	15	5	5	14	14	140	5
		10	11	16	17	140	10
		15	15	19	21	140	16
IMS_abs7	18	5	5	12	14	266	5
		10	10	16	17	266	10
		15	15	20	21	266	16
IMS_abs9	23	5	5	14	14	0	5
		10	10	16	17	0	10
		15	15	18	21	0	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	7	14	0	5
		10	10	20	17	0	10
		15	17	20	21	0	16
IMS_abs11	35	5	5	7	14	0	5
		10	10	12	17	0	10
		15	15	18	21	0	16
IMS_abs12	35	5	5	10	14	44	5
		10	10	11	17	44	10
		15	15	16	21	44	16
IMS_abs13	35	5	5	0	14	0	5
		10	10	0	17	0	10
		15	17	17	21	0	16
IMS_abs14	19	5	0	0	14	258	5
		10	12	12	17	258	10
		15	20	20	21	258	16
IMS_abs15	19	5	0	0	14	250	5
		10	0	0	17	250	10
		15	0	0	21	250	16
mean run time (msec)			9.344	14.420	0.531	544.875	0.113
mean relative run time			82.566	127.417	4.695	4814.688	1.000

Table 68: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix table 2.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	15.36	11.50	6.64	90.43	15.64
10	10.93	9.21	5.79	90.43	10.64
15	6.93	8.00	6.64	90.43	5.93

Table 69: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix table 2.

3.1.3 Baseline3

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 103: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 104: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 105: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	16	5	8	19	17	22	5
		10	12	21	21	22	11
		15	17	22	23	22	16
IMS_abs2	16	5	6	9	17	36	5
		10	10	20	21	36	11
		15	15	20	23	36	16
IMS_abs3	13	5	5	8	17	18	5
		10	10	17	21	18	11
		15	15	17	23	18	16
IMS_abs4	17	5	5	6	17	16	5
		10	10	26	21	16	11
		15	15	31	23	16	16
IMS_abs5	17	5	9	20	17	14	5
		10	18	24	21	14	11
		15	18	25	23	14	16
IMS_abs6	17	5	9	20	17	22	5
		10	10	22	21	22	11
		15	18	22	23	22	16
IMS_abs7	17	5	9	20	17	21	5
		10	14	21	21	21	11
		15	15	21	23	21	16
IMS_abs9	19	5	5	6	17	19	5
		10	10	11	21	19	11
		15	15	16	23	19	16
IMS_abs10	16	5	6	8	17	18	5
		10	11	14	21	18	11
		15	16	17	23	18	16
IMS_abs11	19	5	5	21	17	16	5
		10	10	25	21	16	11
		15	15	27	23	16	16
IMS_abs12	19	5	5	6	17	13	5
		10	10	26	21	13	11
		15	15	30	23	13	16
IMS_abs13	19	5	6	6	17	13	5
		10	10	26	21	13	11
		15	15	30	23	13	16
IMS_abs14	19	5	6	6	17	15	5
		10	14	25	21	15	11
		15	15	30	23	15	16
IMS_abs15	19	5	0	0	17	58	5
		10	10	25	21	58	11
		15	19	22	23	58	16
mean run time (msec)			3.099	5.414	0.725	47.673	0.121
mean relative run time			25.688	44.880	6.007	395.171	1.000

Table 70: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 3.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	11.36	8.29	1.36	7.43	12.36
10	6.14	5.71	3.64	7.43	6.36
15	2.14	6.64	5.64	7.43	1.79

Table 71: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 3.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 106: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 107: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 108: Mushrooms mix Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	17	5	7	10	12	82	5
		10	12	15	13	82	12
		15	17	20	19	82	15
IMS_abs2	17	5	5	10	12	22	5
		10	10	15	13	22	12
		15	15	19	19	22	15
IMS_abs3	24	5	9	12	12	119	5
		10	12	17	13	119	12
		15	17	19	19	119	15
IMS_abs4	24	5	8	10	12	21	5
		10	12	14	13	21	12
		15	17	18	19	21	15
IMS_abs5	24	5	7	10	12	34	5
		10	12	14	13	34	12
		15	16	18	19	34	15
IMS_abs6	24	5	5	10	12	0	5
		10	10	14	13	0	12
		15	15	18	19	0	15
IMS_abs7	24	5	5	8	12	266	5
		10	10	15	13	266	12
		15	17	18	19	266	15
IMS_abs9	18	5	5	12	12	0	5
		10	11	17	13	0	12
		15	16	20	19	0	15
IMS_abs10	18	5	5	10	12	0	5
		10	10	16	13	0	12
		15	15	20	19	0	15
IMS_abs11	24	5	5	6	12	180	5
		10	12	16	13	180	12
		15	15	18	19	180	15
IMS_abs12	22	5	7	12	12	162	5
		10	12	14	13	162	12
		15	17	21	19	162	15
IMS_abs13	22	5	5	11	12	290	5
		10	14	16	13	290	12
		15	15	21	19	290	15
IMS_abs14	17	5	5	0	12	259	5
		10	10	12	13	259	12
		15	15	0	19	259	15
IMS_abs15	17	5	0	0	12	253	5
		10	10	0	13	253	12
		15	0	0	19	253	15
mean run time (msec)			5.196	11.610	0.432	603.481	0.119
mean relative run time			43.503	97.194	3.617	5052.261	1.000

Table 72: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix table 3.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	15.29	12.21	8.86	108.71	15.86
10	9.64	6.93	7.86	108.71	8.86
15	6.07	5.71	3.29	108.71	5.86

Table 73: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix table 3.

3.1.4 Baseline4

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 109: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 110: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 111: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	18	5	10	21	14	33	6
		10	15	22	20	33	10
		15	20	24	19	33	16
IMS_abs2	18	5	5	21	14	25	6
		10	10	22	20	25	10
		15	18	24	19	25	16
IMS_abs3	15	5	7	16	14	44	6
		10	10	18	20	44	10
		15	15	19	19	44	16
IMS_abs4	19	5	5	6	14	13	6
		10	10	11	20	13	10
		15	15	16	19	13	16
IMS_abs5	19	5	5	6	14	24	6
		10	15	26	20	24	10
		15	20	31	19	24	16
IMS_abs6	19	5	10	22	14	22	6
		10	15	24	20	22	10
		15	15	25	19	22	16
IMS_abs7	19	5	5	21	14	15	6
		10	10	22	20	15	10
		15	20	23	19	15	16
IMS_abs9	19	5	6	7	14	72	6
		10	10	12	20	72	10
		15	15	17	19	72	16
IMS_abs10	16	5	6	9	14	21	6
		10	12	14	20	21	10
		15	17	19	19	21	16
IMS_abs11	19	5	5	22	14	22	6
		10	10	25	20	22	10
		15	15	27	19	22	16
IMS_abs12	19	5	5	6	14	17	6
		10	10	27	20	17	10
		15	15	32	19	17	16
IMS_abs13	19	5	6	6	14	17	6
		10	10	11	20	17	10
		15	15	16	19	17	16
IMS_abs14	19	5	6	6	14	14	6
		10	10	11	20	14	10
		15	16	16	19	14	16
IMS_abs15	19	5	6	6	14	57	6
		10	10	0	20	57	10
		15	16	16	19	57	16
mean run time (msec)			1.145	4.592	0.564	66.270	0.139
mean relative run time			8.249	33.094	4.066	477.586	1.000

Table 74: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 4.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	12.14	8.00	4.36	12.64	12.36
10	7.14	6.57	1.64	12.64	8.36
15	2.50	5.43	0.64	12.64	2.50

Table 75: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 4.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 112: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 113: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 114: Mushrooms mix Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	27	5	6	8	7	39	6
		10	11	12	19	39	12
		15	20	34	18	39	16
IMS_abs2	27	5	5	7	7	40	6
		10	10	12	19	40	12
		15	15	34	18	40	16
IMS_abs3	27	5	5	12	7	90	6
		10	11	13	19	90	12
		15	16	17	18	90	16
IMS_abs4	27	5	6	8	7	67	6
		10	11	12	19	67	12
		15	16	16	18	67	16
IMS_abs5	27	5	5	7	7	87	6
		10	11	12	19	87	12
		15	16	17	18	87	16
IMS_abs6	27	5	5	8	7	0	6
		10	11	13	19	0	12
		15	16	17	18	0	16
IMS_abs7	27	5	5	14	7	268	6
		10	10	14	19	268	12
		15	17	17	18	268	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	7	18	7	31	6
		10	12	20	19	31	12
		15	17	20	18	31	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	5	20	7	85	6
		10	10	22	19	85	12
		15	15	26	18	85	16
IMS_abs11	24	5	8	10	7	0	6
		10	11	13	19	0	12
		15	15	18	18	0	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	6	10	7	0	6
		10	13	19	19	0	12
		15	16	20	18	0	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	5	10	7	277	6
		10	10	19	19	277	12
		15	15	20	18	277	16
IMS_abs14	17	5	5	6	7	254	6
		10	10	19	19	254	12
		15	15	24	18	254	16
IMS_abs15	17	5	5	0	7	254	6
		10	18	18	19	254	12
		15	23	23	18	254	16
mean run time (msec)			1.148	4.328	0.420	495.963	0.136
mean relative run time			8.471	31.921	3.097	3658.065	1.000

Table 76: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix table 4.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	17.21	13.21	15.79	93.64	16.79
10	11.57	8.79	4.93	93.64	10.79
15	7.07	7.00	5.07	93.64	6.79

Table 77: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix table 4.

3.1.5 Baseline5

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 115: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 116: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, flask. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 117: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	18	5	8	20	17	42	6
		10	14	21	15	42	11
		15	18	23	23	42	16
IMS_abs2	18	5	5	17	17	46	6
		10	10	21	15	46	11
		15	15	25	23	46	16
IMS_abs3	17	5	6	14	17	16	6
		10	13	15	15	16	11
		15	15	17	23	16	16
IMS_abs4	17	5	5	9	17	14	6
		10	10	25	15	14	11
		15	18	28	23	14	16
IMS_abs5	17	5	8	11	17	12	6
		10	12	23	15	12	11
		15	18	23	23	12	16
IMS_abs6	17	5	8	11	17	13	6
		10	12	20	15	13	11
		15	18	21	23	13	16
IMS_abs7	17	5	8	10	17	20	6
		10	10	19	15	20	11
		15	18	20	23	20	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	5	6	17	17	6
		10	10	11	15	17	11
		15	15	46	23	17	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	7	17	17	6
		10	11	15	15	17	11
		15	16	16	23	17	16
IMS_abs11	18	5	8	20	17	21	6
		10	17	23	15	21	11
		15	18	24	23	21	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	5	21	17	12	6
		10	10	26	15	12	11
		15	15	29	23	12	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	5	11	17	12	6
		10	10	26	15	12	11
		15	15	30	23	12	16
IMS_abs14	17	5	8	10	17	18	6
		10	10	26	15	18	11
		15	15	29	23	18	16
IMS_abs15	17	5	5	10	17	65	6
		10	14	25	15	65	11
		15	15	28	23	65	16
mean run time (msec)			1.454	3.619	0.621	54.975	0.126
mean relative run time			11.499	28.620	4.909	434.784	1.000

Table 78: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix flask 5.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	11.07	5.86	0.50	9.57	11.50
10	5.86	5.36	2.50	9.57	6.50
15	1.71	8.43	5.50	9.57	1.50

Table 79: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix flask 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 118: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 5.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 119: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 10.

Mushrooms mix, table. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 120: Mushrooms mix Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	20	5	6	6	12	32	6
		10	11	11	15	32	11
		15	16	16	24	32	15
IMS_abs2	20	5	7	7	12	36	6
		10	11	12	15	36	11
		15	16	16	24	36	15
IMS_abs3	20	5	6	8	12	92	6
		10	11	12	15	92	11
		15	19	23	24	92	15
IMS_abs4	20	5	6	11	12	28	6
		10	11	12	15	28	11
		15	22	25	24	28	15
IMS_abs5	20	5	5	6	12	35	6
		10	11	13	15	35	11
		15	15	25	24	35	15
IMS_abs6	20	5	11	11	12	0	6
		10	11	13	15	0	11
		15	21	24	24	0	15
IMS_abs7	20	5	0	0	12	266	6
		10	16	16	15	266	11
		15	15	25	24	266	15
IMS_abs9	26	5	8	12	12	149	6
		10	13	16	15	149	11
		15	15	20	24	149	15
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	8	12	0	6
		10	12	21	15	0	11
		15	16	20	24	0	15
IMS_abs11	25	5	5	11	12	0	6
		10	10	16	15	0	11
		15	15	34	24	0	15
IMS_abs12	25	5	7	11	12	99	6
		10	12	15	15	99	11
		15	17	20	24	99	15
IMS_abs13	25	5	8	12	12	280	6
		10	12	17	15	280	11
		15	17	21	24	280	15
IMS_abs14	19	5	5	0	12	256	6
		10	10	16	15	256	11
		15	15	21	24	256	15
IMS_abs15	19	5	0	0	12	250	6
		10	10	14	15	250	11
		15	15	0	24	250	15
mean run time (msec)			5.126	9.643	0.552	498.140	0.120
mean relative run time			42.688	80.302	4.596	4148.283	1.000

Table 80: Change found for each moving window. Mushrooms mix table 5.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	15.50	13.86	9.21	96.57	15.21
10	9.71	7.07	6.21	96.57	10.21
15	4.93	5.50	3.50	96.57	6.21

Table 81: MAE of each algorithm for Mushrooms mix table 5.

3.2 Black chanterelle

3.2.1 Baseline1

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 121: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 122: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 123: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	18	5	6	8	18	93	6
		10	11	26	15	93	11
		15	16	29	23	93	16
IMS_abs2	18	5	5	6	18	82	6
		10	10	12	15	82	11
		15	15	17	23	82	16
IMS_abs3	18	5	6	6	18	15	6
		10	10	12	15	15	11
		15	15	30	23	15	16
IMS_abs4	18	5	6	6	18	14	6
		10	11	13	15	14	11
		15	21	30	23	14	16
IMS_abs5	18	5	6	6	18	14	6
		10	10	29	15	14	11
		15	15	29	23	14	16
IMS_abs6	18	5	6	6	18	14	6
		10	16	26	15	14	11
		15	21	29	23	14	16
IMS_abs7	18	5	10	22	18	33	6
		10	10	24	15	33	11
		15	20	28	23	33	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	5	6	18	16	6
		10	10	12	15	16	11
		15	15	16	23	16	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	7	18	17	6
		10	11	15	15	17	11
		15	16	17	23	17	16
IMS_abs11	18	5	5	22	18	14	6
		10	10	25	15	14	11
		15	20	28	23	14	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	6	6	18	12	6
		10	10	11	15	12	11
		15	15	32	23	12	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	6	6	18	12	6
		10	11	12	15	12	11
		15	15	33	23	12	16
IMS_abs14	18	5	6	6	18	16	6
		10	11	12	15	16	11
		15	15	33	23	16	16
IMS_abs15	18	5	6	7	18	57	6
		10	11	12	15	57	11
		15	15	33	23	57	16
mean run time (msec)			1.427	3.294	0.608	70.479	0.158
mean relative run time			9.019	20.818	3.845	445.421	1.000

Table 82: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle flask 1.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	11.93	10.57	0.00	16.36	12.00
10	7.14	6.50	3.00	16.36	7.00
15	2.71	10.00	5.00	16.36	2.00

Table 83: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle flask 1.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 124: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 125: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 126: Black chanterelle Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	15	5	8	14	13	23	6
		10	12	18	16	23	11
		15	17	20	21	23	16
IMS_abs2	15	5	5	12	13	72	6
		10	10	15	16	72	11
		15	15	21	21	72	16
IMS_abs3	30	5	5	17	13	20	6
		10	13	18	16	20	11
		15	16	20	21	20	16
IMS_abs4	30	5	11	16	13	20	6
		10	12	18	16	20	11
		15	15	20	21	20	16
IMS_abs5	30	5	5	16	13	22	6
		10	12	18	16	22	11
		15	15	20	21	22	16
IMS_abs6	30	5	11	16	13	0	6
		10	12	18	16	0	11
		15	17	20	21	0	16
IMS_abs7	30	5	5	15	13	274	6
		10	10	17	16	274	11
		15	15	21	21	274	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	5	6	13	0	6
		10	10	11	16	0	11
		15	15	27	21	0	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	5	20	13	179	6
		10	12	20	16	179	11
		15	18	22	21	179	16
IMS_abs11	18	5	8	10	13	0	6
		10	10	14	16	0	11
		15	15	24	21	0	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	7	9	13	0	6
		10	13	14	16	0	11
		15	15	19	21	0	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	5	9	13	275	6
		10	10	12	16	275	11
		15	15	18	21	275	16
IMS_abs14	18	5	5	0	13	255	6
		10	10	0	16	255	11
		15	17	17	21	255	16
IMS_abs15	18	5	0	0	13	251	6
		10	0	0	16	251	11
		15	16	16	21	251	16
mean run time (msec)			5.080	10.197	0.502	551.685	0.127
mean relative run time			40.028	80.343	3.958	4346.777	1.000

Table 84: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle table 1.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	15.79	10.71	8.86	93.50	15.86
10	11.43	8.79	6.14	93.50	10.86
15	6.36	5.93	5.57	93.50	6.14

Table 85: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle table 1.

3.2.2 Baseline2

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 127: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 128: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 129: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	15	5	6	8	16	213	6
		10	11	11	13	213	11
		15	16	31	27	213	16
IMS_abs2	21	5	6	8	16	0	6
		10	11	11	13	0	11
		15	15	16	27	0	16
IMS_abs3	18	5	6	13	16	14	6
		10	11	13	13	14	11
		15	15	30	27	14	16
IMS_abs4	18	5	7	7	16	14	6
		10	10	11	13	14	11
		15	17	28	27	14	16
IMS_abs5	18	5	7	8	16	14	6
		10	12	24	13	14	11
		15	17	28	27	14	16
IMS_abs6	18	5	7	9	16	14	6
		10	12	23	13	14	11
		15	17	22	27	14	16
IMS_abs7	18	5	7	9	16	19	6
		10	12	20	13	19	11
		15	17	19	27	19	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	6	7	16	16	6
		10	11	14	13	16	11
		15	15	16	27	16	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	8	16	17	6
		10	11	16	13	17	11
		15	16	17	27	17	16
IMS_abs11	18	5	5	21	16	14	6
		10	10	25	13	14	11
		15	18	28	27	14	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	5	6	16	14	6
		10	10	11	13	14	11
		15	15	30	27	14	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	6	6	16	14	6
		10	11	11	13	14	11
		15	15	31	27	14	16
IMS_abs14	18	5	6	6	16	14	6
		10	11	11	13	14	11
		15	15	31	27	14	16
IMS_abs15	18	5	6	6	16	54	6
		10	11	11	13	54	11
		15	15	31	27	54	16
mean run time (msec)			1.220	3.107	0.670	188.136	0.139
mean relative run time			8.799	22.401	4.833	1356.615	1.000

Table 86: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle flask 2.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	11.86	9.71	2.14	20.79	12.00
10	7.00	5.71	5.00	20.79	7.00
15	2.21	8.71	9.00	20.79	2.14

Table 87: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle flask 2.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 130: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 131: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 132: Black chanterelle Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	10	5	6	8	9	18	7
		10	11	13	14	18	11
		15	16	17	19	18	16
IMS_abs2	10	5	5	7	9	117	7
		10	10	11	14	117	11
		15	15	16	19	117	16
IMS_abs3	25	5	6	12	9	0	7
		10	11	14	14	0	11
		15	16	17	19	0	16
IMS_abs4	25	5	6	8	9	17	7
		10	11	13	14	17	11
		15	16	17	19	17	16
IMS_abs5	25	5	6	9	9	26	7
		10	11	13	14	26	11
		15	16	17	19	26	16
IMS_abs6	25	5	5	9	9	0	7
		10	11	14	14	0	11
		15	16	17	19	0	16
IMS_abs7	25	5	5	9	9	264	7
		10	10	14	14	264	11
		15	15	17	19	264	16
IMS_abs9	15	5	5	13	9	0	7
		10	13	16	14	0	11
		15	16	20	19	0	16
IMS_abs10	15	5	7	11	9	94	7
		10	10	16	14	94	11
		15	18	20	19	94	16
IMS_abs11	55	5	5	12	9	0	7
		10	12	16	14	0	11
		15	15	20	19	0	16
IMS_abs12	55	5	8	11	9	102	7
		10	10	20	14	102	11
		15	18	20	19	102	16
IMS_abs13	55	5	5	11	9	281	7
		10	10	20	14	281	11
		15	15	21	19	281	16
IMS_abs14	55	5	5	0	9	252	7
		10	10	0	14	252	11
		15	15	0	19	252	16
IMS_abs15	55	5	0	0	9	251	7
		10	0	0	14	251	11
		15	0	0	19	251	16
mean run time (msec)			9.311	13.178	0.407	619.370	0.168
mean relative run time			55.266	78.217	2.418	3676.167	1.000

Table 88: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle table 2.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	26.86	23.57	23.14	87.71	25.14
10	22.29	20.14	19.29	87.71	21.43
15	19.50	19.79	16.86	87.71	18.14

Table 89: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle table 2.

3.2.3 Baseline3

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 133: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 134: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 135: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	18	5	6	6	20	55	5
		10	13	27	23	55	11
		15	20	32	22	55	16
IMS_abs2	18	5	6	6	20	237	5
		10	15	22	23	237	11
		15	15	23	22	237	16
IMS_abs3	18	5	6	7	20	18	5
		10	11	16	23	18	11
		15	16	17	22	18	16
IMS_abs4	18	5	6	6	20	17	5
		10	10	11	23	17	11
		15	15	16	22	17	16
IMS_abs5	18	5	6	6	20	17	5
		10	10	11	23	17	11
		15	15	16	22	17	16
IMS_abs6	18	5	6	6	20	17	5
		10	10	27	23	17	11
		15	19	32	22	17	16
IMS_abs7	18	5	0	0	20	17	5
		10	14	27	23	17	11
		15	15	31	22	17	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	6	7	20	19	5
		10	10	12	23	19	11
		15	15	17	22	19	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	7	20	17	5
		10	12	12	23	17	11
		15	17	19	22	17	16
IMS_abs11	18	5	5	6	20	17	5
		10	14	28	23	17	11
		15	15	34	22	17	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	6	6	20	17	5
		10	11	11	23	17	11
		15	16	16	22	17	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	6	6	20	17	5
		10	11	12	23	17	11
		15	16	16	22	17	16
IMS_abs14	18	5	6	6	20	17	5
		10	11	12	23	17	11
		15	16	16	22	17	16
IMS_abs15	18	5	6	6	20	68	5
		10	11	12	23	68	11
		15	16	16	22	68	16
mean run time (msec)			4.319	4.503	0.766	118.032	0.130
mean relative run time			33.236	34.656	5.892	908.371	1.000

Table 90: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle flask 3.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	12.50	12.21	2.00	22.57	13.00
10	6.36	6.71	5.00	22.57	7.00
15	2.29	5.50	4.00	22.57	2.00

Table 91: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle flask 3.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 136: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 137: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 138: Black chanterelle Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	27	5	7	10	11	19	6
		10	12	14	15	19	10
		15	16	18	19	19	16
IMS_abs2	27	5	7	11	11	19	6
		10	11	15	15	19	10
		15	16	18	19	19	16
IMS_abs3	27	5	5	11	11	21	6
		10	10	14	15	21	10
		15	15	16	19	21	16
IMS_abs4	27	5	7	12	11	16	6
		10	11	14	15	16	10
		15	16	18	19	16	16
IMS_abs5	27	5	7	12	11	18	6
		10	11	14	15	18	10
		15	16	18	19	18	16
IMS_abs6	27	5	5	11	11	0	6
		10	11	14	15	0	10
		15	16	18	19	0	16
IMS_abs7	27	5	5	11	11	266	6
		10	10	15	15	266	10
		15	16	18	19	266	16
IMS_abs9	15	5	5	12	11	0	6
		10	10	16	15	0	10
		15	16	21	19	0	16
IMS_abs10	15	5	7	11	11	48	6
		10	12	16	15	48	10
		15	16	18	19	48	16
IMS_abs11	15	5	5	6	11	0	6
		10	10	0	15	0	10
		15	15	16	19	0	16
IMS_abs12	25	5	5	6	11	0	6
		10	15	20	15	0	10
		15	20	22	19	0	16
IMS_abs13	20	5	6	6	11	272	6
		10	10	25	15	272	10
		15	15	24	19	272	16
IMS_abs14	27	5	6	6	11	253	6
		10	11	11	15	253	10
		15	16	16	19	253	16
IMS_abs15	27	5	10	10	11	251	6
		10	15	15	15	251	10
		15	20	20	19	251	16
mean run time (msec)			1.394	4.186	0.514	509.729	0.119
mean relative run time			11.689	35.092	4.305	4273.071	1.000

Table 92: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle table 3.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	17.57	14.14	12.79	78.43	17.79
10	12.43	10.29	8.79	78.43	13.79
15	7.71	7.14	6.50	78.43	8.21

Table 93: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle table 3.

3.2.4 Baseline4

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 139: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 140: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 141: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	14	5	6	17	18	56	6
		10	12	19	22	56	11
		15	16	24	23	56	16
IMS_abs2	17	5	5	7	18	13	6
		10	10	12	22	13	11
		15	15	16	23	13	16
IMS_abs3	17	5	5	6	18	13	6
		10	10	12	22	13	11
		15	18	27	23	13	16
IMS_abs4	17	5	8	10	18	13	6
		10	10	25	22	13	11
		15	18	27	23	13	16
IMS_abs5	17	5	8	10	18	13	6
		10	19	24	22	13	11
		15	18	27	23	13	16
IMS_abs6	17	5	5	10	18	13	6
		10	10	23	22	13	11
		15	18	27	23	13	16
IMS_abs7	17	5	8	10	18	30	6
		10	10	23	22	30	11
		15	15	22	23	30	16
IMS_abs9	19	5	6	6	18	16	6
		10	11	13	22	16	11
		15	15	16	23	16	16
IMS_abs10	19	5	6	15	18	17	6
		10	11	16	22	17	11
		15	16	17	23	17	16
IMS_abs11	17	5	5	22	18	13	6
		10	10	24	22	13	11
		15	19	27	23	13	16
IMS_abs12	17	5	5	6	18	13	6
		10	10	11	22	13	11
		15	15	29	23	13	16
IMS_abs13	17	5	6	6	18	13	6
		10	11	12	22	13	11
		15	15	30	23	13	16
IMS_abs14	17	5	6	6	18	15	6
		10	11	12	22	15	11
		15	15	30	23	15	16
IMS_abs15	17	5	6	6	18	51	6
		10	11	12	22	51	11
		15	15	16	23	51	16
mean run time (msec)			1.412	3.024	0.717	45.092	0.127
mean relative run time			11.080	23.740	5.624	353.951	1.000

Table 94: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle flask 4.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	11.00	8.43	1.21	9.14	11.07
10	6.21	5.64	4.93	9.14	6.07
15	1.93	7.86	5.93	9.14	1.36

Table 95: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle flask 4.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 142: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 143: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 144: Black chanterelle Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	21	5	6	6	8	28	6
		10	19	26	11	28	10
		15	20	27	21	28	15
IMS_abs2	18	5	6	6	8	29	6
		10	10	24	11	29	10
		15	15	26	21	29	15
IMS_abs3	23	5	6	6	8	218	6
		10	10	28	11	218	10
		15	15	30	21	218	15
IMS_abs4	18	5	6	6	8	28	6
		10	14	24	11	28	10
		15	19	26	21	28	15
IMS_abs5	18	5	9	21	8	36	6
		10	10	22	11	36	10
		15	15	25	21	36	15
IMS_abs6	18	5	5	6	8	0	6
		10	10	23	11	0	10
		15	15	25	21	0	15
IMS_abs7	18	5	6	6	8	261	6
		10	10	0	11	261	10
		15	15	26	21	261	15
IMS_abs9	18	5	8	15	8	294	6
		10	13	20	11	294	10
		15	18	22	21	294	15
IMS_abs10	18	5	5	15	8	0	6
		10	10	20	11	0	10
		15	15	22	21	0	15
IMS_abs11	18	5	5	7	8	0	6
		10	10	21	11	0	10
		15	15	26	21	0	15
IMS_abs12	25	5	8	10	8	0	6
		10	13	17	11	0	10
		15	17	20	21	0	15
IMS_abs13	25	5	6	9	8	275	6
		10	10	15	11	275	10
		15	15	18	21	275	15
IMS_abs14	18	5	5	7	8	254	6
		10	10	0	11	254	10
		15	15	0	21	254	15
IMS_abs15	18	5	5	0	8	250	6
		10	0	0	11	250	10
		15	0	0	21	250	15
mean run time (msec)			4.731	13.639	0.377	647.558	0.124
mean relative run time			38.041	109.663	3.029	5206.498	1.000

Table 96: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle table 4.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	13.43	11.43	11.57	111.21	13.57
10	8.93	7.86	8.57	111.21	9.57
15	4.79	8.21	2.86	111.21	4.57

Table 97: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle table 4.

3.2.5 Baseline5

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 145: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 146: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, flask. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 147: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	15	5	7	9	9	45	6
		10	11	16	23	45	11
		15	16	18	23	45	16
IMS_abs2	21	5	6	8	9	14	6
		10	11	12	23	14	11
		15	15	16	23	14	16
IMS_abs3	18	5	5	6	9	14	6
		10	10	11	23	14	11
		15	19	28	23	14	16
IMS_abs4	18	5	5	6	9	14	6
		10	19	26	23	14	11
		15	19	28	23	14	16
IMS_abs5	18	5	9	21	9	13	6
		10	10	25	23	13	11
		15	19	28	23	13	16
IMS_abs6	18	5	5	12	9	14	6
		10	19	24	23	14	11
		15	19	28	23	14	16
IMS_abs7	18	5	9	10	9	30	6
		10	10	23	23	30	11
		15	15	22	23	30	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	6	6	9	17	6
		10	10	11	23	17	11
		15	15	32	23	17	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	7	9	17	6
		10	11	16	23	17	11
		15	16	17	23	17	16
IMS_abs11	18	5	8	20	9	14	6
		10	18	23	23	14	11
		15	18	27	23	14	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	5	21	9	11	6
		10	10	26	23	11	11
		15	15	29	23	11	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	6	6	9	11	6
		10	11	11	23	11	11
		15	15	30	23	11	16
IMS_abs14	18	5	6	6	9	16	6
		10	11	12	23	16	11
		15	15	30	23	16	16
IMS_abs15	18	5	6	6	9	59	6
		10	11	12	23	59	11
		15	15	16	23	59	16
mean run time (msec)			1.419	3.026	0.612	47.903	0.129
mean relative run time			11.019	23.507	4.753	372.070	1.000

Table 98: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle flask 5.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	11.64	8.86	9.00	9.21	12.00
10	6.00	6.00	5.00	9.21	7.00
15	2.21	8.07	5.00	9.21	2.14

Table 99: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle flask 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 148: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 5.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 149: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 10.

Black Chanterelle, table. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 150: Black chanterelle Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	32	5	6	12	7	22	6
		10	13	15	15	22	11
		15	16	18	30	22	16
IMS_abs2	32	5	6	10	7	22	6
		10	11	13	15	22	11
		15	15	16	30	22	16
IMS_abs3	32	5	6	8	7	100	6
		10	13	13	15	100	11
		15	17	18	30	100	16
IMS_abs4	32	5	6	9	7	27	6
		10	11	13	15	27	11
		15	15	17	30	27	16
IMS_abs5	32	5	6	9	7	96	6
		10	11	13	15	96	11
		15	15	17	30	96	16
IMS_abs6	32	5	5	8	7	267	6
		10	10	13	15	267	11
		15	15	16	30	267	16
IMS_abs7	32	5	5	0	7	260	6
		10	10	0	15	260	11
		15	30	39	30	260	16
IMS_abs9	26	5	6	10	7	0	6
		10	12	17	15	0	11
		15	15	20	30	0	16
IMS_abs10	26	5	6	7	7	270	6
		10	10	15	15	270	11
		15	15	16	30	270	16
IMS_abs11	26	5	6	6	7	0	6
		10	10	11	15	0	11
		15	18	32	30	0	16
IMS_abs12	17	5	8	19	7	199	6
		10	13	21	15	199	11
		15	18	21	30	199	16
IMS_abs13	26	5	5	11	7	274	6
		10	10	25	15	274	11
		15	15	25	30	274	16
IMS_abs14	26	5	5	0	7	253	6
		10	10	0	15	253	11
		15	15	0	30	253	16
IMS_abs15	26	5	0	0	7	251	6
		10	0	0	15	251	11
		15	0	0	30	251	16
mean run time (msec)			6.568	16.914	0.523	562.074	0.128
mean relative run time			51.175	131.784	4.073	4379.272	1.000

Table 100: Change found for each moving window. Black chanterelle table 5.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	22.93	20.86	21.36	128.43	22.36
10	18.07	16.86	13.36	128.43	17.36
15	12.86	12.57	3.64	128.43	12.36

Table 101: MAE of each algorithm for Black chanterelle table 5.

3.3 Yellowfoot

3.3.1 Baseline1

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 151: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 152: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 153: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	16	5	6	19	13	19	7
		10	11	20	26	19	13
		15	16	21	25	19	16
IMS_abs2	16	5	5	17	13	19	7
		10	10	19	26	19	13
		15	15	20	25	19	16
IMS_abs3	16	5	6	14	13	15	7
		10	11	14	26	15	13
		15	15	17	25	15	16
IMS_abs4	16	5	5	13	13	15	7
		10	10	14	26	15	13
		15	15	34	25	15	16
IMS_abs5	16	5	5	24	13	15	7
		10	10	43	26	15	13
		15	20	30	25	15	16
IMS_abs6	16	5	9	22	13	15	7
		10	21	26	26	15	13
		15	20	30	25	15	16
IMS_abs7	16	5	5	21	13	16	7
		10	10	25	26	16	13
		15	19	29	25	16	16
IMS_abs9	14	5	6	14	13	17	7
		10	11	16	26	17	13
		15	15	18	25	17	16
IMS_abs10	14	5	6	16	13	17	7
		10	11	17	26	17	13
		15	16	18	25	17	16
IMS_abs11	18	5	5	21	13	15	7
		10	10	24	26	15	13
		15	15	29	25	15	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	6	7	13	15	7
		10	10	13	26	15	13
		15	15	34	25	15	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	6	7	13	15	7
		10	11	14	26	15	13
		15	16	16	25	15	16
IMS_abs14	18	5	6	7	13	15	7
		10	11	14	26	15	13
		15	16	16	25	15	16
IMS_abs15	18	5	6	7	13	15	7
		10	11	14	26	15	13
		15	16	16	25	15	16
mean run time (msec)			0.993	3.083	0.695	35.262	0.148
mean relative run time			6.720	20.857	4.699	238.549	1.000

Table 102: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 1.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	10.57	5.50	3.43	2.21	9.43
10	5.86	6.07	9.57	2.21	3.43
15	2.07	7.86	8.57	2.21	1.00

Table 103: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 1.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 1. Window size: 5

Figure 154: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 1. Window size: 10

Figure 155: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 1. Window size: 15

Figure 156: Yellowfoot Baseline1. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	22	5	7	16	8	28	7
		10	12	24	14	28	12
		15	16	25	25	28	15
IMS_abs2	22	5	5	7	8	32	7
		10	10	28	14	32	12
		15	15	28	25	32	15
IMS_abs3	18	5	7	8	8	182	7
		10	11	14	14	182	12
		15	16	19	25	182	15
IMS_abs4	20	5	5	11	8	26	7
		10	12	16	14	26	12
		15	16	22	25	26	15
IMS_abs5	20	5	7	10	8	28	7
		10	10	16	14	28	12
		15	16	24	25	28	15
IMS_abs6	20	5	7	11	8	0	7
		10	11	16	14	0	12
		15	16	23	25	0	15
IMS_abs7	20	5	5	13	8	278	7
		10	10	15	14	278	12
		15	15	24	25	278	15
IMS_abs9	18	5	6	9	8	33	7
		10	11	12	14	33	12
		15	16	19	25	33	15
IMS_abs10	25	5	5	9	8	0	7
		10	10	13	14	0	12
		15	15	0	25	0	15
IMS_abs11	30	5	7	8	8	30	7
		10	12	18	14	30	12
		15	17	20	25	30	15
IMS_abs12	30	5	7	10	8	23	7
		10	12	14	14	23	12
		15	17	19	25	23	15
IMS_abs13	17	5	5	9	8	101	7
		10	10	14	14	101	12
		15	15	19	25	101	15
IMS_abs14	17	5	5	11	8	263	7
		10	10	14	14	263	12
		15	15	19	25	263	15
IMS_abs15	17	5	5	0	8	251	7
		10	10	0	14	251	12
		15	15	0	25	251	15
mean run time (msec)			1.494	11.932	0.506	505.556	0.135
mean relative run time			11.094	88.630	3.759	3755.233	1.000

Table 104: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 1.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	15.21	11.71	13.14	77.36	14.14
10	10.36	7.00	7.14	77.36	9.14
15	5.43	6.50	5.29	77.36	6.14

Table 105: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 1.

3.3.2 Baseline2

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 157: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 158: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 159: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	15	5	6	14	19	20	6
		10	11	19	22	20	11
		15	16	20	24	20	16
IMS_abs2	15	5	5	9	19	19	6
		10	10	17	22	19	11
		15	15	18	24	19	16
IMS_abs3	14	5	5	15	19	16	6
		10	11	16	22	16	11
		15	15	18	24	16	16
IMS_abs4	18	5	5	6	19	16	6
		10	10	12	22	16	11
		15	15	16	24	16	16
IMS_abs5	17	5	5	21	19	16	6
		10	10	26	22	16	11
		15	18	30	24	16	16
IMS_abs6	17	5	8	21	19	16	6
		10	13	25	22	16	11
		15	18	28	24	16	16
IMS_abs7	17	5	8	20	19	22	6
		10	13	25	22	22	11
		15	18	26	24	22	16
IMS_abs9	15	5	5	6	19	18	6
		10	10	12	22	18	11
		15	15	16	24	18	16
IMS_abs10	15	5	6	6	19	18	6
		10	10	17	22	18	11
		15	16	17	24	18	16
IMS_abs11	17	5	6	6	19	16	6
		10	10	11	22	16	11
		15	15	31	24	16	16
IMS_abs12	18	5	6	6	19	16	6
		10	11	11	22	16	11
		15	15	32	24	16	16
IMS_abs13	18	5	6	6	19	16	6
		10	11	11	22	16	11
		15	15	32	24	16	16
IMS_abs14	18	5	6	6	19	16	6
		10	11	11	22	16	11
		15	15	32	24	16	16
IMS_abs15	18	5	6	6	19	18	6
		10	11	11	22	18	11
		15	15	31	24	18	16
mean run time (msec)			1.059	2.584	0.688	37.392	0.130
mean relative run time			8.152	19.886	5.294	287.769	1.000

Table 106: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 2.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	10.64	7.71	2.43	2.36	10.57
10	5.71	5.57	5.43	2.36	5.57
15	1.64	8.50	7.43	2.36	1.43

Table 107: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 2.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 2. Window size: 5

Figure 160: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 2. Window size: 10

Figure 161: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 2. Window size: 15

Figure 162: Yellowfoot Baseline2. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	18	5	6	7	7	156	6
		10	20	30	20	156	11
		15	21	34	25	156	15
IMS_abs2	18	5	6	7	7	147	6
		10	10	12	20	147	11
		15	15	34	25	147	15
IMS_abs3	18	5	5	19	7	246	6
		10	14	20	20	246	11
		15	19	21	25	246	15
IMS_abs4	19	5	6	6	7	64	6
		10	10	11	20	64	11
		15	15	34	25	64	15
IMS_abs5	19	5	6	6	7	66	6
		10	11	11	20	66	11
		15	15	16	25	66	15
IMS_abs6	19	5	6	6	7	0	6
		10	11	11	20	0	11
		15	16	16	25	0	15
IMS_abs7	19	5	6	6	7	274	6
		10	11	11	20	274	11
		15	0	0	25	274	15
IMS_abs9	17	5	9	15	7	20	6
		10	12	19	20	20	11
		15	17	20	25	20	15
IMS_abs10	17	5	6	15	7	20	6
		10	11	17	20	20	11
		15	15	19	25	20	15
IMS_abs11	18	5	5	11	7	21	6
		10	10	16	20	21	11
		15	15	20	25	21	15
IMS_abs12	18	5	7	16	7	20	6
		10	12	19	20	20	11
		15	17	20	25	20	15
IMS_abs13	18	5	5	18	7	52	6
		10	12	19	20	52	11
		15	17	20	25	52	15
IMS_abs14	18	5	7	14	7	261	6
		10	10	19	20	261	11
		15	15	20	25	261	15
IMS_abs15	18	5	5	10	7	247	6
		10	10	15	20	247	11
		15	15	20	25	247	15
mean run time (msec)			3.260	4.770	0.587	392.754	0.119
mean relative run time			27.383	40.071	4.931	3299.058	1.000

Table 108: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 2.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	12.07	7.14	11.14	98.43	12.14
10	6.71	4.43	1.86	98.43	7.14
15	3.57	6.43	6.86	98.43	3.14

Table 109: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 2.

3.3.3 Baseline3

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 163: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 164: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 165: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	16	5	6	19	18	25	6
		10	13	22	14	25	11
		15	16	24	16	25	16
IMS_abs2	16	5	6	18	18	21	6
		10	11	20	14	21	11
		15	15	22	16	21	16
IMS_abs3	13	5	6	14	18	15	6
		10	11	14	14	15	11
		15	15	17	16	15	16
IMS_abs4	17	5	5	6	18	15	6
		10	10	11	14	15	11
		15	15	30	16	15	16
IMS_abs5	17	5	7	9	18	13	6
		10	12	25	14	13	11
		15	18	29	16	13	16
IMS_abs6	17	5	7	11	18	15	6
		10	12	24	14	15	11
		15	17	27	16	15	16
IMS_abs7	17	5	5	19	18	21	6
		10	12	23	14	21	11
		15	17	22	16	21	16
IMS_abs9	14	5	5	6	18	18	6
		10	10	16	14	18	11
		15	15	16	16	18	16
IMS_abs10	14	5	6	7	18	18	6
		10	11	17	14	18	11
		15	16	17	16	18	16
IMS_abs11	16	5	7	8	18	15	6
		10	10	26	14	15	11
		15	17	29	16	15	16
IMS_abs12	17	5	5	7	18	15	6
		10	10	11	14	15	11
		15	15	30	16	15	16
IMS_abs13	17	5	7	7	18	15	6
		10	10	11	14	15	11
		15	15	30	16	15	16
IMS_abs14	17	5	7	7	18	15	6
		10	12	12	14	15	11
		15	17	29	16	15	16
IMS_abs15	17	5	7	7	18	35	6
		10	12	12	14	35	11
		15	15	19	16	35	16
mean run time (msec)			1.335	3.104	0.593	46.953	0.134
mean relative run time			9.948	23.140	4.423	350.006	1.000

Table 110: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 3.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	9.93	6.86	1.93	4.36	10.07
10	4.93	5.36	2.21	4.36	5.07
15	1.14	8.29	1.07	4.36	1.07

Table 111: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 3.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 3. Window size: 5

Figure 166: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 3. Window size: 10

Figure 167: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 3. Window size: 15

Figure 168: Yellowfoot Baseline3. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	15	5	10	13	12	72	8
		10	12	17	13	72	12
		15	17	20	22	72	18
IMS_abs2	15	5	9	12	12	24	8
		10	10	15	13	24	12
		15	15	19	22	24	18
IMS_abs3	35	5	5	8	12	164	8
		10	10	18	13	164	12
		15	15	18	22	164	18
IMS_abs4	35	5	9	12	12	26	8
		10	11	15	13	26	12
		15	15	19	22	26	18
IMS_abs5	35	5	9	11	12	26	8
		10	11	13	13	26	12
		15	15	18	22	26	18
IMS_abs6	35	5	9	11	12	0	8
		10	10	12	13	0	12
		15	15	18	22	0	18
IMS_abs7	35	5	5	11	12	270	8
		10	10	12	13	270	12
		15	15	19	22	270	18
IMS_abs9	10	5	7	10	12	26	8
		10	13	15	13	26	12
		15	17	19	22	26	18
IMS_abs10	10	5	5	10	12	26	8
		10	10	14	13	26	12
		15	15	19	22	26	18
IMS_abs11	22	5	5	9	12	24	8
		10	10	21	13	24	12
		15	16	20	22	24	18
IMS_abs12	22	5	7	12	12	21	8
		10	12	17	13	21	12
		15	17	19	22	21	18
IMS_abs13	22	5	5	12	12	73	8
		10	12	17	13	73	12
		15	17	19	22	73	18
IMS_abs14	22	5	5	15	12	260	8
		10	10	17	13	260	12
		15	15	20	22	260	18
IMS_abs15	18	5	5	0	12	251	8
		10	10	0	13	251	12
		15	15	0	22	251	18
mean run time (msec)			1.108	8.271	0.467	317.604	0.163
mean relative run time			6.800	50.768	2.866	1949.454	1.000

Table 112: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 3.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	16.86	13.21	12.21	74.29	15.64
10	13.29	10.71	11.50	74.29	12.21
15	10.00	9.86	7.64	74.29	8.79

Table 113: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 3.

3.3.4 Baseline4

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 169: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 170: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 171: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	10	5	6	13	8	20	6
		10	11	15	18	20	11
		15	16	18	22	20	17
IMS_abs2	10	5	6	10	8	14	6
		10	10	13	18	14	11
		15	15	17	22	14	17
IMS_abs3	15	5	5	8	8	9	6
		10	10	23	18	9	11
		15	23	26	22	9	17
IMS_abs4	16	5	5	6	8	9	6
		10	17	20	18	9	11
		15	16	23	22	9	17
IMS_abs5	16	5	6	18	8	9	6
		10	11	19	18	9	11
		15	16	23	22	9	17
IMS_abs6	16	5	6	17	8	19	6
		10	11	18	18	19	11
		15	16	20	22	19	17
IMS_abs7	16	5	6	16	8	18	6
		10	11	17	18	18	11
		15	16	18	22	18	17
IMS_abs9	16	5	5	6	8	11	6
		10	10	26	18	11	11
		15	15	28	22	11	17
IMS_abs10	16	5	6	10	8	11	6
		10	10	11	18	11	11
		15	15	29	22	11	17
IMS_abs11	16	5	6	7	8	29	6
		10	12	20	18	29	11
		15	17	24	22	29	17
IMS_abs12	17	5	5	7	8	11	6
		10	10	24	18	11	11
		15	17	27	22	11	17
IMS_abs13	17	5	5	7	8	11	6
		10	18	24	18	11	11
		15	15	26	22	11	17
IMS_abs14	17	5	5	7	8	13	6
		10	10	23	18	13	11
		15	17	26	22	13	17
IMS_abs15	17	5	6	7	8	27	6
		10	12	22	18	27	11
		15	17	25	22	27	17
mean run time (msec)			1.435	3.709	0.552	43.289	0.158
mean relative run time			9.094	23.511	3.501	274.408	1.000

Table 114: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 4.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	9.79	6.29	7.36	6.29	9.36
10	4.14	5.00	2.64	6.29	4.64
15	1.71	8.21	6.64	6.29	1.64

Table 115: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 4.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 4. Window size: 5

Figure 172: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 4. Window size: 10

Figure 173: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 4. Window size: 15

Figure 174: Yellowfoot Baseline4. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	18	5	9	22	11	45	6
		10	14	24	16	45	14
		15	19	24	20	45	17
IMS_abs2	17	5	5	12	11	47	6
		10	10	19	16	47	14
		15	15	22	20	47	17
IMS_abs3	18	5	6	6	11	88	6
		10	10	30	16	88	14
		15	16	31	20	88	17
IMS_abs4	18	5	8	23	11	44	6
		10	14	24	16	44	14
		15	19	24	20	44	17
IMS_abs5	17	5	5	12	11	68	6
		10	10	16	16	68	14
		15	15	23	20	68	17
IMS_abs6	17	5	9	12	11	0	6
		10	12	16	16	0	14
		15	15	22	20	0	17
IMS_abs7	17	5	5	12	11	269	6
		10	12	14	16	269	14
		15	15	22	20	269	17
IMS_abs9	18	5	5	14	11	0	6
		10	13	16	16	0	14
		15	15	21	20	0	17
IMS_abs10	18	5	7	8	11	0	6
		10	10	21	16	0	14
		15	18	20	20	0	17
IMS_abs11	25	5	7	13	11	27	6
		10	11	14	16	27	14
		15	16	17	20	27	17
IMS_abs12	24	5	9	12	11	0	6
		10	11	16	16	0	14
		15	16	19	20	0	17
IMS_abs13	17	5	5	11	11	291	6
		10	10	16	16	291	14
		15	16	20	20	291	17
IMS_abs14	17	5	5	11	11	262	6
		10	10	16	16	262	14
		15	15	20	20	262	17
IMS_abs15	17	5	5	0	11	246	6
		10	10	0	16	246	14
		15	15	0	20	246	17
mean run time (msec)			1.398	9.458	0.500	597.883	0.158
mean relative run time			8.863	59.983	3.173	3791.889	1.000

Table 116: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 4.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	12.00	7.71	7.43	91.64	12.43
10	7.21	5.29	2.43	91.64	4.43
15	2.64	6.21	2.86	91.64	1.43

Table 117: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 4.

3.3.5 Baseline5

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 175: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 176: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, flask. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 177: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	16	5	6	19	10	21	6
		10	17	22	14	21	11
		15	17	22	26	21	16
IMS_abs2	15	5	6	9	10	22	6
		10	10	21	14	22	11
		15	16	20	26	22	16
IMS_abs3	13	5	5	14	10	15	6
		10	11	14	14	15	11
		15	15	17	26	15	16
IMS_abs4	18	5	5	6	10	15	6
		10	10	11	14	15	11
		15	15	30	26	15	16
IMS_abs5	17	5	5	21	10	15	6
		10	10	25	14	15	11
		15	18	29	26	15	16
IMS_abs6	17	5	8	20	10	15	6
		10	13	24	14	15	11
		15	18	26	26	15	16
IMS_abs7	17	5	8	19	10	21	6
		10	12	23	14	21	11
		15	18	22	26	21	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	5	6	10	17	6
		10	10	11	14	17	11
		15	15	16	26	17	16
IMS_abs10	18	5	6	6	10	17	6
		10	11	13	14	17	11
		15	16	16	26	17	16
IMS_abs11	17	5	8	13	10	15	6
		10	10	24	14	15	11
		15	18	29	26	15	16
IMS_abs12	17	5	5	6	10	15	6
		10	10	11	14	15	11
		15	15	31	26	15	16
IMS_abs13	17	5	5	6	10	15	6
		10	10	11	14	15	11
		15	18	31	26	15	16
IMS_abs14	17	5	7	9	10	15	6
		10	12	13	14	15	11
		15	15	29	26	15	16
IMS_abs15	17	5	7	8	10	46	6
		10	10	13	14	46	11
		15	17	29	26	46	16
mean run time (msec)			1.179	2.967	0.552	44.596	0.131
mean relative run time			9.021	22.697	4.224	341.120	1.000

Table 118: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot flask 5.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	10.57	7.00	6.71	4.57	10.71
10	5.71	5.71	2.86	4.57	5.71
15	1.50	8.64	9.29	4.57	1.29

Table 119: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot flask 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 5. Window size: 5

Figure 178: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 5.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 5. Window size: 10

Figure 179: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 10.

Yellowfoot, table. Set 5. Window size: 15

Figure 180: Yellowfoot Baseline5. Window size 15.

reading	gt	window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
IMS_abs1	19	5	7	11	12	23	5
		10	11	15	18	23	13
		15	17	20	17	23	16
IMS_abs2	19	5	5	12	12	25	5
		10	12	18	18	25	13
		15	17	20	17	25	16
IMS_abs3	21	5	5	10	12	284	5
		10	10	15	18	284	13
		15	15	19	17	284	16
IMS_abs4	24	5	6	14	12	22	5
		10	11	17	18	22	13
		15	16	19	17	22	16
IMS_abs5	24	5	8	12	12	246	5
		10	10	17	18	246	13
		15	15	19	17	246	16
IMS_abs6	24	5	5	12	12	0	5
		10	10	15	18	0	13
		15	15	19	17	0	16
IMS_abs7	24	5	5	12	12	265	5
		10	10	15	18	265	13
		15	15	18	17	265	16
IMS_abs9	18	5	5	6	12	0	5
		10	10	19	18	0	13
		15	16	24	17	0	16
IMS_abs10	25	5	5	0	12	0	5
		10	10	17	18	0	13
		15	15	16	17	0	16
IMS_abs11	17	5	6	8	12	0	5
		10	11	13	18	0	13
		15	16	18	17	0	16
IMS_abs12	17	5	6	10	12	240	5
		10	11	16	18	240	13
		15	16	20	17	240	16
IMS_abs13	17	5	9	10	12	289	5
		10	12	14	18	289	13
		15	15	20	17	289	16
IMS_abs14	17	5	5	0	12	257	5
		10	10	17	18	257	13
		15	22	22	17	257	16
IMS_abs15	17	5	0	0	12	248	5
		10	18	18	18	248	13
		15	23	23	17	248	16
mean run time (msec)			3.496	8.460	0.700	852.923	0.146
mean relative run time			23.897	57.825	4.785	5829.576	1.000

Table 120: Change found for each moving window. Yellowfoot table 5.

moving window size	shewhart	cusum	max mcusum	bayes	mfcusum
5	14.71	11.86	8.21	127.71	15.21
10	9.21	4.36	2.93	127.71	7.21
15	5.14	4.14	3.21	127.71	4.21

Table 121: MAE of each algorithm for Yellowfoot table 5.